

Master Thesis

Magneto-transport study in 2D magnetic semiconductor multi-terminal FET

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Abstract

Two-dimensional (2D) materials have garnered immense interest due to their pronounced quantum effects and extraordinary properties. However, the existence of true 2D magnetic materials remained elusive until 2017. Since the discovery of CrGeTe₃ and CrI₃, 2D magnets have captivated researchers with their theoretical significance and tunability to external stimuli. This thesis focuses on fabricating multiterminal field effect transistors (FETs) based on the magnetic semiconductor CrPS₄ to investigate its 2D magnetism. The large bandwidth of CrPS₄ allows us to conduct in-plane transport measurements down to cryogenic temperatures, enabling the determination of crucial magnetic properties, including the Néel temperature, spin-flop field (H_{flop}), and spin-flip field (H_{flip}). Unprecedentedly, we perform 4-probe measurements on CrPS₄ FETs and demonstrate that the presence of large contact resistance does not disrupt previous measurement results, confirming that the observed large magnetoconductance indeed originates from CrPS₄ itself. We also confirmed the accuracy and effectiveness of determining H_{flop} and H_{flip} from magneto-transport measurements. However, we could not reproduce all the known results due to the inclusion of a vertical signal due to the device geometry employed to successfully implement 4-probe measurements.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 2D van der Waals Materials

Reducing the dimensionality of a system from three-dimensional (3D) to two-dimensional leads to the enhancement of quantum effects and the emergence of exceptional electronic, optical, and magnetic properties [1], making 2D systems highly interesting. Before the discovery of true stable 2D crystals, researchers extensively studied quasi-2D systems that are formed at the interfaces between two materials, such as two-dimensional electron gas systems (2DESs) formed between two different semiconductors [2]. In the searching for stable 2D crystals, van der Waals materials have garnered attention owing to their unique crystalline structures consisting of different atom layers stacking on top of each other, where atoms are tightly held together by strong in-plane covalent bonds and are weakly held together by out-of-plane van der Waals interactions. The special structure of layered van der Waals materials has led researchers to explore the possibility of separating these materials into atomically thin layers or even monolayers, although it was still uncertain whether these 2D materials could exist or not [3]. In 2004, micromechanical cleavage, also known as the Scotch tape method, was firstly utilized for separating few-layered graphene flakes from graphite [4]. This approach is later widely utilized in academic research, also in this thesis. Interestingly, these atomically thin graphene flakes not only confirmed the existence of 2D crystals but also showed exceptionally good and exciting electronic properties including ballistic transport [4] and quantum Hall effect [5], which has significantly generated researchers' interest in 2D materials.

Following the discovery of graphene, many other 2D van der Waals materials with diverse and captivating properties have been found. For example, transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) are van der Waals materials with the formula MX_2 , where M is a transition metal (such as Mo, W) and X represents a chalcogen element (such as S, Se, Te). Transition metal dichalcogenides exhibit a layered structure where each individual

layer consists of three atomic layers arranged in an X-M-X (chalcogen-transition metal-chalcogen) structure. Namely, one hexagonally packed plane of transition metal atoms is sandwiched between two layers of chalcogen atoms [6]. Bulk-formed TMDs exhibit multiple structural phases. Common structural phases are the semiconducting 2H-phase and the metallic 1T-phase [7]. Bulk-formed 2H-TMDs crystal is an indirect bandgap semiconductor while it transits to a direct bandgap semiconductor when thinned down to the monolayer limit. The diverse structural phases and electronic structures displayed by TMDs greatly broaden the properties of 2D materials. Another example is hexagonal boron nitride (hBN), which is an insulator with a very large bandgap of around 6 eV [8], making it very useful in serving as an electrical insulator in tunneling junctions or as a gate dielectric. Besides, hBN has high chemical and thermal stability. They were proved to be useful to encapsulated other 2D materials, protecting them from environmental factors and enhancing their properties [9]. In this thesis, top and bottom hBN layers are used to fully encapsulate our device for protection, as well as serving as the gate dielectric to tune its charge carrier density.

2D van der Waals materials exhibit a plethora of novel electronic, optical, and other intriguing phenomena that are unexpected and are different from their 3D counterparts [6]. These distinctive properties arise from the reduction in dimensionality and/or the effects of quantum confinement [10]. For example, superconductivity has been observed in atomically thin layers of 2H-NbSe₂, including monolayer, where charge density waves are unusually enhanced from bulk to atomically thin samples [11]; 1T'-WTe₂ has been predicted to be a large-gap quantum spin Hall (QSH) insulator in 2014 [12]. Later in 2017, clear signatures of quantum spin Hall state were observed in monolayer 1T'-WTe₂, which is a topological state very difficult to realize in other systems [13]; monolayer MoS₂, a direct gap semiconductor as thin as 0.65 nm, has been employed to fabricate field-effect transistors with high on/off ratios and ultralow standby power dissipation [14]. The diverse range of quantum phenomenon in low dimension system, as well as their fascinating materials properties have attracted enormous research interest.

With the large family of 2D van der Waals materials, much more versatility and flexibility can be realized by aligning and stacking them on top of each other to create new van der Waals heterostructures (Figure 1.1). The assembly of van der Waals heterostructures has already resulted in more new engineering possibilities and the discovery of numerous fascinating physical phenomena. For example, the relative twisting angle between two 2D materials is a degree of freedom to control. At certain twisted angles, the moiré superlattice potential brings strong correlated interactions between electrons, resulting in correlated insulating states and unconventional superconductivity [16][17][18]; graphene and 2D semiconductors can be stacked together to form van der Waals contacts, providing ultra-clean and non-damaging methods to fabricate electrodes on top of 2D semiconductors [19]. The lattice mismatch in the heterostructures can bring local strain to the consist-

Figure 1.1: Building van der Waals heterostructures from consisting 2D van der Waals materials. [15]

ing layers, adjusting their structures. This phenomenon was observed experimentally in graphene–hBN heterostructures [20]. Exploring the diverse possibilities of van der Waals heterostructures is not only of great theoretical interest but also paves the way for the development of novel electronic and optoelectronic devices.

1.2 2D Magnetic Semiconductors

As mentioned in section 1.1, the rapid growth of the 2D van der Waals materials family has covered a diverse range of interesting properties, which cover a broad spectrum, including insulators, metals, semimetals, superconductors, topological insulators, etc. However, one conspicuously absent member of this collection was the 2D magnetic van der Waals materials [21]. Researchers have shown continuous interest in the pursuit of true 2D magnetic systems because the transition from a 3D magnetic system to a 2D magnetic system is nontrivial. For example, for a 3D system, a magnetic phase transition always exists at a finite temperature [22]. However, in a 2D system, the existence of a magnetic phase transition depends on the spin dimensionality. Mermin-Wagner theorem rigorously proved the 2D-Heisenberg-like magnetic system could not establish any long-range magnetic order at any finite temperature [23]. Only if magnetic anisotropy is introduced, it is possible that magnetic orders be established in a 2D system [24]. So, studying the transition of magnetic properties from 3D to 2D systems is very interesting. Moreover, the magnetic properties of 2D systems are easily manipulated through external factors such

as magnetic field, electric field, and charge carrier density [22], which will be discussed in detail in Chapter 2.

The discovery of bilayer magnetic material CrGeTe₃ [25] and monolayer magnetic material CrI₃ [26] in 2017 has sparked tremendous excitement because they are intrinsic 2D magnets that allow for fundamental studies of magnetism in the true 2D limit [27]. Both materials belong to the class of layered van der Waals materials, thereby filling the previous absence. The Curie temperature T_C of CrGeTe₃ has been found to exhibit a strong dependence on its thickness [25]. Additionally, the magnetic structure of CrI₃ displays the characteristic of an even-odd alternative magnetic structure [26]. These phenomena prove the strong dependence of magnetism on dimensionality. Researchers also observed 2D magnetic materials' tunability through external influences, including magnetic fields, electric fields, and doping. For example, a large enough external magnetic field can induce spin-flop and spin-flip magnetic phase transition in some 2D magnetic materials with weak magnetic anisotropy energy [28] such as CrPS₄ [29]. Moreover, a large doping level can substantially change materials' magnetic properties such as in CrI₃ [30] and in Fe₃GeTe₂ [31].

2D magnetic van der Waals materials cover a wide range of transport properties, including insulators, conductors, and semiconductors. The first studied two 2D magnetic materials-CrGeTe₃ and CrI₃ are both insulators. 2D magnetic insulators exhibit intriguing phenomena and hold significant theoretical value. For example, the CrI₃-based magnetic tunneling junctions show very large magnetoconductance [32]; monolayer magnetic insulator CrCl₃ shows the critical scaling characteristics fitting well with a 2D-XY system rather than 2D-Ising, indicating the realization of a finite-size Berezinskii-Kosterlitz-Thouless phase transition [33]. During the initial phase of research in 2D magnets, 2D magnetic insulators were extensively investigated using two techniques: magnetic tunneling junctions and the magneto-optical Kerr effect. These methods played a crucial role in detecting and characterizing 2D magnetism. However, in some cases, the utilization of field-effect transistors to detect 2D magnetism is better, as will be discussed in detail in Section 2.3.

In addition to 2D magnetic insulators, conducting 2D magnetic materials are also discovered and get much attention. For example, 2D magnetic conductor Fe₃GeTe₂ was successfully exfoliated and characterized in 2018 [31]. Researchers found doping can significantly shift the ferromagnetic transition temperature, even raising it to room temperature [31]. The in-plane anomalous Hall effect was used to characterize the net magnetization in this experiment [31].

Some 2D magnetic van der Waals materials also show the characteristics of semiconductors. However, the semiconducting properties of 2D magnetic van der Waals materials receive less attention, because most of them have relatively large band gaps and extremely narrow bandwidths [34]. In the narrow-bandwidth bands, electrons are lo-

calized and show very small mobility, which strongly limits their applications in FETs. Actually, FETs are very useful to investigate the complex interplay between their magnetic and semiconducting properties, as will be mentioned below and discussed in section 2.3. In order to fabricate magnetic semiconductor-based FETs that are functional even at cryogenic temperatures, researchers started to look for 2D magnetic semiconductors with larger bandwidths. So far, only CrSBr [34], CrPS₄ [35], and NiI₂ [36] are found to have large bandwidths above 1 eV. And the FETs based on them could behave well below the magnetic phase transition temperatures T_c . One of the advantages of FETs is that, in 2D antiferromagnetic materials, the vanishing net magnetization makes it difficult to detect magnetism with widely used magneto-optical methods. But in CrPS₄ FETs, the magnetoconductance can reveal the spin-flop phase transition of antiferromagnetic material CrPS₄ [35]; in NiI₂ FETs, thickness-dependent multiferroic phase transition can be observed [37]; in CrSBr FETs, strong anisotropy in transport can be revealed [34]. In section 2.3, we will discuss in detail how much information can be extracted from FETs. Field-effect transistors provide valuable platforms for studying the complex interplay between magnetic and semiconducting properties. In this thesis, we use FETs based on CrPS₄ to study their magnetic and electronic properties. So far, all the known CrPS₄ FETs are limited to single-gate two-terminal devices with graphene as contacts, because the fabrication of contacts on CrPS₄ is a major challenge (conventional methods are not effective, which will be introduced in Chapter 2). In this thesis, we fabricated double-gate multi-terminal CrPS₄ FETs with three expectations: Firstly, doing four-terminal measurements to exclude contact resistance. Secondly, having the possibility to perform anisotropic transport measurements. And finally, tuning the electric field and charge carrier density independently. To address the challenge of fabricating contacts on CrPS₄, we utilized pre-patterned bottom contacts made of platinum.

1.3 Thesis outline

In this project, we fabricated multi-terminal double-gated field-effect transistors based on 2D antiferromagnetic semiconductor-CrPS₄, which have never been successfully realized before. Earlier work [35] reported the complete determination of magnetic phase diagrams of multilayer CrPS₄, as well as the gate-controlled magnetism phenomena. Besides, large magnetoconductance is also reported in CrPS₄ FETs [38]. However, they could not remove the influence of contact resistance in their two-terminal FETs. In this thesis, we employed pre-patterned bottom contacts to fabricate multi-terminal FETs, allowing us to perform 4-probe measurements to partially remove the influence of contact resistance. By comparing 2-probe and 4-probe measurement results, we confirmed that the magnetic order is strongly coupled with the magnetoconductance, which allows us to accurately determine the spin-flop phase transition and the spin-flip phase transition fields. Our 4-probe measurements provide evidence that the observed phenomena are in-

deed intrinsic to CrPS₄ and are not from contact resistance. However, our results also showed some distinctions from Wu et al.'s studies [35][38], which can be attributed to the combined effects of vertical transport behavior and in-plane transport behavior.

Chapter 2 presents a comprehensive overview of the relevant background information for this thesis. It begins by introducing the concept of magnetism, with a particular focus on 2D magnetism. The chapter then explores the utilization of transport measurements for detecting 2D magnetism, discussing both vertical tunneling junctions and in-plane FETs as devices. Next, the phenomenon of gate-controlled magnetism in 2D materials is introduced. Subsequently, a detailed introduction to the known properties of CrPS₄ is provided, covering aspects such as its crystal structure, magnetic order, band structure, magnetic phase diagram, and previously reported transport measurements from CrPS₄ FETs.

Chapter 3 focuses on the nano-fabrication processes and experimental setups utilized in this thesis. The chapter begins by providing an explanation for our adoption of pre-patterned bottom contact geometry to fabricate multiterminal CrPS₄ FETs. It goes on to describe in detail the procedures of obtaining and identifying thin flakes of CrPS₄. This is followed by an introduction to the techniques employed for the assembly of heterostructures and a description of the procedures of contact deposition. Finally, the chapter outlines the setups used for transport measurements.

Chapter 4 presents the transport data of the CrPS₄ FET devices down to 2 K, enabling us to study the magnetic properties with transport. Although the comparison between 4-probe and 2-probe data demonstrates the presence of large contact resistance, the characterization of the magnetic properties of CrPS₄ remains reliable. We analyzed the magneto-transport data at different temperatures and top gate voltages. The large magnetoconductance obtained from both 2-probe and 4-probe agrees with previous studies [35][38]. Besides, we can accurately determine H_{flop} and H_{flip} from magneto-transport measurements, which agree very well with Wu et al.'s results [35]. However, we do not observe the gate-tunability of the H_{flop} and H_{flip} . Furthermore, due to the configuration of top-gate voltages and bottom contacts, magnetoconductance oscillations are observed, which is the signature of c-axis tunneling.

Chapter 2

Electronic and magnetic properties of 2D van der Waals semiconductors

2.1 Introduction to magnetism, from 3D to 2D systems

Magnetism is known for thousands of years since our ancestors' discovery of lodestones that attracts iron. The Chinese during the Han dynasty harnessed this natural phenomenon and invented the lodestone compass for navigation before they really understood the physics mechanism behind it [39]. It was during the 19th century that James Clerk Maxwell summarized previous research and published Maxwell's equations, which provided a comprehensive understanding of magnetism within the framework of the electromagnetic field [40]. However, this understanding was proved to be incomplete with the establishment of quantum mechanics in the 20th century. According to quantum mechanics, it was revealed magnetism originates from the spin and orbital angular momentum of electrons [41] or the moving charges [42]. In other words, magnetism is fundamentally a quantum mechanical phenomenon, which plays a vital role in various aspects of people's modern life, including applications in information technology such as magnetic storage and magnetoresistive random-access memory (MRAM), in medical applications such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), in renewable energy generation such as wind turbines, etc.

In a 3D crystal, individual magnetic moments can be formed at the consisting atoms. In the simplest scenario, these individual magnetic moments are independent and non-interacting with one another. This type of material is referred to as a paramagnetic material. At finite temperatures and in the absence of the external magnetic field, the magnetic moments are randomly oriented without a preferred direction, which means this system lacks long-range order.

When the magnetic moments interact with each other, they tend to align themselves in

particular arrangements that minimize the material's overall energy. The main source of this interaction is the exchange interaction. The interaction that favors certain alignments between neighbors can lead to spontaneous magnetic long-range order at $T = 0 \text{ K}$. A typical model that considers only nearest-neighbor exchange interactions is the Heisenberg model with the Hamiltonian [43]:

$$\hat{H} = -J \sum_{\langle i,j \rangle} \vec{S}_i \cdot \vec{S}_j \quad (2.1)$$

, where the $\vec{S}_{i,j}$ represents the spin operator, J is the exchange integral, and $\langle i, j \rangle$ means summing over only the nearest-neighbor interaction. It is worth mentioning that $\vec{S}_{i,j}$ is a vector that can take different dimensionalities depending on the space where the magnetic moments live in. This dimension is also called spin dimensionality, which will be discussed later in this section.

In the absence of an external magnetic field ($\mu H = 0 \text{ T}$) and at zero temperature $T = 0 \text{ K}$, if $J > 0$, the magnetic moments prefer parallel alignment. This results in the formation of ferromagnetic order, which exhibits macroscopic net magnetization. Conversely, when $J < 0$, the system displays an antiferromagnetic ground state with zero net magnetization (Figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1: Schematic diagram of (a) ferromagnetic order and (b) antiferromagnetic order in the absence of an external magnetic field and at zero temperature

At finite temperatures ($T \neq 0 \text{ K}$), thermal fluctuations bring complexity to the system. The magnetic structure is excited from its ground state. This leads to the individual magnetic moments deviating from perfect alignment, resulting in the creation of magnons, which is the quasi-particles describing the collective excitations of the magnetic structure of the system. When the temperature reaches a critical point T_c , the magnetic susceptibility χ diverges so that previous microscopic fluctuations now appear macroscopically [44], which are strong enough to destroy the long-range magnetic ordering in the system. The critical temperature of ferromagnetic materials is Curie temperature T_C while the critical temperature of antiferromagnetic materials is Néel temperature T_N . Above the critical temperature T_c , the system transitions back to the paramagnetic phase, where the

χ follows the Curie-Weiss law:

$$\chi = \frac{C}{T - \theta_{CW}} \quad (2.2)$$

, where the parameter C is known as the Curie constant and the parameter θ_{CW} is referred to as the Curie-Weiss temperature. The magnitude of θ_{CW} is related to the strength of the molecular field, which can be taken as an indicator of the strength of J [44]. For ferromagnetic materials, θ_{CW} is positive. One often finds that $T_C \approx \theta_{CW}$. For antiferromagnetic materials, θ_{CW} is negative. The Néel temperature is usually smaller than the absolute value of Curie-Weiss temperature: $T_C < |\theta_{CW}|$, due to an oversimplification of how the molecular field is define and the effect of frustration [44].

Figure 2.2: Theoretical magnetic susceptibility of a (a) paramagnetic material (PM), (b) ferromagnetic material (FM), and (c) antiferromagnetic material (AFM). Above the critical temperature T_c , the system returns to the paramagnetic phase, where the magnetic susceptibility χ obeys Curie-Weiss law (d). χ_{\perp} and χ_{\parallel} represent the magnetic susceptibility vertical and parallel to the spin alignment direction respectively. [45][44]

The change of magnetic order is a process also known as a magnetic phase transition. One of the most fascinating physics of magnetic phase transitions is the concept of universality [46], where many seemingly different systems exhibit the same critical exponents near their critical points. This phenomenon occurs regardless of the specific details of each system, indicating the underlying similarities between them. One such similarity is dimensionality, which plays a crucial role in determining critical behavior.

Systems with different dimensionalities exhibit distinct magnetic behaviors. In 3D systems, magnetic phase transitions can always occur at any finite temperature [22]. However, in 2D systems that are associated with stronger intrinsic spin fluctuations, the existence of a magnetic phase transition depends on the spin dimensionality (Figure 2.3). The Mermin-Wagner theorem states that in 2D systems with continuous rotational symmetries (described by a Lie group) and short-range interactions, spontaneous magnetization can not happen [23]. However, in discrete symmetry systems (described by an algebraic group) such as the Ising model, the magnetic order can be established. The es-

Figure 2.3: Schematic diagram of a square lattice hosting three models with different spin dimensionalities. (a) Ising model where spin can only take two discrete values: up or down. (b) XY model where spin can continuously take any orientation in the xy plane. (c) Heisenberg model where there is no constraint on the direction of the spins [22].

establishment of magnetic order in the Ising model is fundamentally due to the presence of magnetic anisotropy. Theoretically speaking, magnetic anisotropy arises from the spin-orbit coupling (SOC), which leads to the formation of orbital magnetism and the coupling of the spin with the lattice, thereby establishing magnetic anisotropy [47]. The magnetic anisotropy gaps out the low-energy modes in the spin-wave spectrum, stabilizing the system and establishing magnetic order [24], which is a very important parameter determining the formation of magnetic orders in 2D systems.

The interesting physics phenomenon provided by 2D magnetic systems, such as the dependence of magnetism on the thickness and dimensionality, the important influence of magnetic anisotropy, the emergence of novel 2D magnetic phase transitions and critical behavior, as well as the possibilities of manipulating 2D magnetism, have greatly fascinated researchers. In the past 30 years, many efforts have been devoted to studying the 2D magnetic structure and 2D magnetic phase transitions in magnetic thin films grown on a substrate [48][49]. However, the quality of the magnetic thin films is highly dependent on the specific details of the growth conditions. While it is still possible to grow high-quality intrinsic magnetic thin films with orderly arranged and exchange-coupled magnetic atoms, it requires researchers to carefully find the appropriate growth method [50]. On the other hand, preparing extrinsic magnetic thin films is not that difficult, but the presence of randomly distributed magnetic impurities in the sample results in large inhomogeneity in the electronic structure and magnetic properties [50]. Due to these challenges associated with preparing genuine intrinsic 2D magnetic systems, there is a need to explore new material families for studying 2D magnetism.

2.2 Magnetic order in 2D van der Waals materials

In the past decade, researchers started to search for intrinsic 2D magnetic crystals in the family of 2D van der Waals materials [51][52][53]. As introduced in section 1.1, van der Waals materials are crystals consisting of 2D layers that are tightly bonded within the layer, while their binding in the vertical direction is weak van der Waals forces. This

unique structure makes them possible to be exfoliated down to the limit of monolayers. If magnetism can persist down to monolayers, they can be regarded as true 2D intrinsic magnetic systems. Certain exfoliation methods, such as Au-assisted mechanical exfoliation, offer highly versatile, contamination-free, and one-step exfoliation. It can be applied to a wide range of van der Waals materials, simplifying the sample preparation process compared to the traditional growth of magnetic thin films [54]. In short, exfoliating magnetic van der Waals is a promising method to produce intrinsic 2D magnetic systems simply.

In 2017, researchers successfully exfoliated atomically thin layers of CrGeTe_3 [25] and CrI_3 [26]. They provide clear experimental evidence that magnetism persists down to the atomically thin limit. For CrGeTe_3 , researchers utilize the scanning Kerr microscope to image and measure the magnetism of atomically thin and micrometer-sized flakes. The ferromagnetic order in CrGeTe_3 sample was clearly observed in Figure 2.4. Through a

Figure 2.4: Observation of ferromagnetism in atomically thin CrGeTe_3 . (a) Optical image of exfoliated atomically thin CrGeTe_3 sample on a 260-nm-thick SiO_2/Si substrate. (b) to (e) Map of Kerr rotation signal obtained from scanning Kerr microscope. The measurements are performed as the temperature gradually decreases from 40 K to 4.7 K under a 0.075 T magnetic field. [25]

combination of optical contrast and atomic force microscopy, the thickness of the atomically thin layer is confirmed to be a bilayer sample with a thicker end. At the temperature of 40 K, the Kerr intensity is only observable for thicker flakes at the end of the strip. As the temperature decreases, the long strip becomes more distinguishable. At 22 K, the bilayer strip becomes clearly discernible from the substrate. This experiment provides direct evidence of the discovery of an intrinsic 2D magnetic crystal [25].

Moreover, magnetic order is also clearly observed in 2D CrI_3 crystals (Figure 2.5). For

Figure 2.5: Layer-dependent magnetic ordering in atomically-thin CrI_3 [26]. The hysteresis loops in monolayer and trilayer samples indicate ferromagnetism while the vanishing Kerr rotation angle in bilayer samples demonstrates antiferromagnetism.

CrI_3 , researchers employ magneto-optical Kerr effect microscopy to monitor the net magnetization in atomically thin samples. In monolayer and trilayer CrI_3 samples, the Kerr rotation angle shows hysteresis loops with a coercive field of approximately 0.1 T , which imply ferromagnetic states (Figure 2.5 a and c). However, distinctly different behavior is observed in bilayer CrI_3 samples, where the Kerr rotation angle is vanishing at small fields, indicating an antiferromagnetic state with vanishing net magnetization (Figure 2.5 b). Their observation was strong evidence that CrI_3 transits from the ferromagnetic state in the monolayer to the antiferromagnetic state in the bilayer, and goes back to the ferromagnetic state in the trilayer and bulk [26]. The atomically thin CrI_3 flakes were also proved to be an intrinsic 2D magnetic crystal.

The discovery of CrI_3 and CrGeTe_3 as intrinsic 2D magnetic materials has significantly inspired researchers to explore more 2D magnets within the family of magnetic van der Waals materials. However, the inheritance of magnetism from bulk-formed magnetic van der Waals materials to their 2D form is not guaranteed. As the thickness of a magnetic material is reduced to its 2D limit, significant changes can occur in its magnetic properties.

Thickness-dependent magnetism is widely observed in various 2D magnetic materials, such as in Fe_3GeTe_2 [31], and EuSn_2As_2 [55], CrCl_3 [56], VI_3 [57], and CrPS_4 [58], etc. This phenomenon testifies the sensitive relationship between magnetic order and dimensionality [47].

To date, numerous other 2D magnetic van der Waals materials with diverse magnetic structures have been discovered. The various magnetic structures of 2D van der Waals materials can be classified according to the sign of the interlayer exchange integral J_\perp and the intralayer exchange integral J_\parallel . Since they have layered structures, the J_\parallel can be very different from J_\perp . The original isotropic Heisenberg model should be rewritten as the anisotropic model:

$$\hat{H} = -J_\parallel \sum_{\langle i,j \rangle} \left(S_i^x \cdot S_j^x + S_i^y \cdot S_j^y \right) - J_\perp \sum_{\langle i,j \rangle} S_i^z \cdot S_j^z \quad (2.3)$$

, where the permutation of the sign of J_\parallel and J_\perp yield diverse magnetic orders (Figure 2.6): when both interlayer and intralayer coupling are ferromagnetic ($J_\parallel > 0$, $J_\perp > 0$), the system is in the ferromagnetic state, such as bulk CrI_3 and Fe_3GeTe_2 ; the interlayer antiferromagnetic coupling and intralayer ferromagnetic coupling ($J_\parallel > 0$, $J_\perp < 0$) yield an A-type antiferromagnetic state, which can be viewed as different ferromagnetic layers stacking together alternatively, such as atomically thin CrI_3 and bulk CrCl_3 ; the C-type

Figure 2.6: Examples of magnetic configurations of vdW layered materials [22]. The different combinations of the sign of J_\parallel and J_\perp yield different ground magnetic states.

antiferromagnetic has interlayer ferromagnetic and intralayer antiferromagnetic coupling ($J_\parallel < 0$, $J_\perp > 0$), such as CoPS_3 and MnPS_3 ; for a G-type antiferromagnetic material, both interlayer and intralayer coupling are antiferromagnetic ($J_\parallel < 0$, $J_\perp < 0$), such as

FePS₃ and MnPSe₃ [22]. These 2D magnetic materials, each with their unique magnetic structures and properties, offer interesting platforms to study 2D magnetism.

2D magnets offer a fascinating platform for studying exchange interactions, spin-orbit coupling, magnetic anisotropy energy, and the manipulation of these parameters. However, in practice, it is challenging for researchers to detect and characterize magnetism in these ultra-thin systems. Conventional methods like neutron powder diffraction (NPD), conventional vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM), and conventional superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID) magnetometry are not applicable to such small and thin samples. In the beginning, researchers successfully applied magneto-optic techniques such as Kerr effect (MOKE) microscopy and magnetic circular dichroism (MCD) spectroscopy to study 2D magnetic van der Waals materials. These methods allowed for the observation and characterization of magnetic structures at the scale of a micrometer, corresponding to the size of the laser spot. Additionally, other methods such as magnetic force microscopy (MFM) and the scanning diamond NV center spin magnetometer have also been employed [59].

In addition to the above mentioned methods, transport techniques can be employed to sensitively detect 2D magnetism. In certain cases, transport measurements can offer greater accuracy and provide additional information for studying 2D magnets. The advantages and disadvantages of using transport measurements to probe magnetism will be discussed in detail in the next section.

2.3 Probing magnetism via transport measurements

During the early stages of research in the field of 2D magnetism, magneto-optical and magneto-electrical measurements emerged as two common methods for detecting 2D magnetism [25][26][32][60][61][62]. The optical methods measure spin-dependent complex optical conductivity and electrical transport measurements probe spin-dependent electric conductivity [27]. Optical measurements rely on various magneto-optic effects, including the Faraday effect [63], Kerr effect [25], Zeeman effect [64], and magneto-birefringence effect [65] to detect or study magnetism. Although optical method is contact-free, low-energy-consumption, and in some cases highly sensitive [66], there are still some limitations, which will be mentioned in this section. In this thesis, we use electrical transport measurements to detect and study 2D magnetism. Typically, the devices for this purpose can be categorized into two groups: magnetic tunneling junctions and field-effect transistors, which will be introduced in detail in this section.

2.3.1 Magnetic tunnel junctions

Spin-filter magnetic tunnel junctions refer to the devices with the structure that a layer of insulating magnet is sandwiched between two conducting non-magnetic layers (Figure 2.7), which offer an ideal platform to study spin-dependent tunneling phenomena and identifying the magnetic structure of the barrier materials. For example, in 2018, different

Figure 2.7: Schematic of a 2D spin-filter magnetic tunnel junction with bilayer CrI_3 as magnetic tunnel barrier sandwiched between the few-layer graphene contacts. [60]

research groups independently reported the observation of remarkably high values of tunnel magnetoresistance (more than 10000 %) in graphene/ CrI_3 /graphene tunnel junction devices with CrI_3 as tunnel barriers [32][61][60][62].

Figure 2.8: Spin-filter magnetic tunnel junctions with different layered CrI_3 crystals as tunnel barrier. (a) to (c): The tunneling current is measured as a function of the out-of-plane magnetic field ($\mu_0 H_{\perp}$) at different selected biases: (a) -290 mV , (b) 235 mV , and (c) 300 mV . All measurements are performed at a temperature of 2 K . The green (orange) curve represents decreasing (increasing) magnetic field. (d) to (e): The reflective magnetic circular dichroism (RMCD) of the corresponding device at zero bias for the cases shown in (a) to (c). Insets show the corresponding magnetic states. [60]

The study conducted by Song et al. [60] explored CrI_3 ranging from bilayer to four-layer. Figure 2.8.a-c show the tunnel current I_t as a function of out-of-plane magnetic field ($\mu_0 H_\perp$), where large magnetoconductance is observed. Figure 2.8.d-f show the reflective magnetic circular dichroism (RMCD) signal as a function of $\mu_0 H_\perp$. At low fields, the RMCD is small, indicating a layered antiferromagnetic ground state, whereas there are steps to larger RMCD signal as the field increases above critical points, corresponding to the modification of magnetic states. It is shown clearly that RMCD steps occur at approximately the same $\mu_0 H_\perp$ as the steps in the I_t , demonstrating the correspondence between the magnetic state and the I_t [60]. As the thickness of the samples increases to four-layer, more intermediate plateaus are observed in both the RMCD and the I_t , which indicates the presence of more complex intermediate magnetic states different from either AFM state or the fully polarized state. It is worth mentioning that magnetoresistance increases quickly from 310% for the bilayer samples to 8600% for the four-layer samples.

The complex intermediate magnetic states and very large tunnel magnetoresistance (also around 8000%) are also observed independently by our group in thicker samples of around 10 layers [32]. As shown in Figure 2.9.a, there are 3 abrupt jumps (J1, J2, and J3, indicated

Figure 2.9: Vertical transport experiments in magnetic tunnel junctions with thin CrI_3 flakes as tunnel barrier (Approximately 10 layers). (a) Tunneling resistance (left axis) and resistance ratio $R(B)/R(2 T)$ (right axis) measured at 10 K. The observed jumps indicated by the vertical arrows (J1, J2, and J3) are consistently present in all four measured devices, with J2 and J3 occurring at the same magnetic field values of approximately 0.85 T and 1.9 T. (b) A color plot of the resistance as a function of magnetic field (B) and temperature (T) reveals three distinct plateaus (labeled I, II, III) at low temperatures, suggesting the presence of complex magnetic states. [32]

by arrows) observed in the magnetoresistance curve. Jump J1 is always accompanied by a hysteresis whereas jumps J2 and J3 occur at the fixed magnetic field, regardless of the sweeping direction. Since these jumps indicate the modification of magnetic states, the whole magnetic phase diagram can be determined (Figure 2.9.b). The phase diagram

clearly shows that magnetic phase boundaries shift to lower fields as the temperature increases and eventually disappears. It is worth mentioning that the determination of the phase diagram of such complex intermediate magnetic states is very difficult to accomplish by other methods [32], demonstrating the advantages of electrical measurements for detecting 2D magnetism over optical methods.

The large magnetoresistance can be understood qualitatively by the spin-filter model:

Figure 2.10: Spin filter model. (a) Different spins experience different barrier heights within a magnetic layer. (b) The two-layer spin filter model involves the use of two magnetic layers. The ferromagnetic state has lower resistance because of the exponential dependence of the tunneling current on the barrier height.

since CrI_3 flakes exhibit A-type antiferromagnetic state, each monolayer of CrI_3 can be viewed as a spin filter for electrons, with different tunnel barrier heights for spin-up and spin-down electrons (Figure 2.10.a). In the antiferromagnetic state, when spin-unpolarized electrons are injected from the graphene contacts, they encounter successive anti-aligned spin filters. On average, they experience approximately the same tunnel barrier, showing a high total resistance. In the ferromagnetic state, the tunnel barrier is high for electrons with the opposite spin (T_{AP} , Figure 2.10.b), whereas it is significantly lower for electrons with the same spin (T_P). According to the exponential dependence of the tunneling current on the barrier height, the ferromagnetic state has significantly reduced resistance [27]. This oversimplified model elucidates the correlation between the transport behavior of electrons and the magnetic state of the material. In Section 2.5, we will introduce that this type of correlation is also observed in the in-plane direction.

Another type of magnetic tunnel junction has a structure where two ferromagnetic layers are separated by a thin non-magnetic insulator. This structure is also known as a spin valve in which electrons tunnel from one ferromagnet to the other. Spin valves also show the characteristic of spin-dependent tunneling, but the mechanism is entirely different from

spin-filter magnetic tunnel junctions. In a spin valve, magnetoresistance arises from the dissimilar electronic structures of the two spin-conducting channels. There is a mismatch between the incoming and outgoing Bloch states of the two ferromagnetic electrodes [67]. In 2018, Wang et al. prepared a $\text{Fe}_3\text{GeTe}_2/\text{hBN}/\text{Fe}_3\text{GeTe}_2$ junction, in which a tunnel magnetoresistance of approximately 160% was observed [68]. Generally speaking, the magnetoresistance is much smaller in spin valves than that in spin-filter magnetic tunnel junctions [22], but spin valves are still an effective way to detect materials' magnetic state.

From the above experiments, we notice the advantage of using transport measurements to detect 2D magnetism: transport measurements have the ability to sensitively detect and discover intricate magnetic phases that are not easily observable using commonly used magneto-optical methods. For example, in four-layer CrI_3 , the $\downarrow\uparrow\uparrow\uparrow$ state and the $\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\uparrow$ state are indistinguishable in RMCD but show different current plateaus [60]. What's more, transport measurements allow the accurate determination of some complex magnetic diagrams, which can provide valuable information about the magnetic exchange and anisotropy energy scales of these systems [69].

2.3.2 Magnetic semiconductor field-effect transistors

In addition to vertical transport measurements that are introduced above, the in-plane transport properties are also interesting and can be used to detect 2D magnetism. In the in-plane direction, the crystal's periodic potential is preserved, and electrons exhibit well-defined quasi-momentum and energy in the electronic bands. So, in-plane transport measurements provide an ideal opportunity to investigate the interplay between the semi-conducting properties and magnetic properties of 2D magnets. In order to do the in-plane transport measurements for magnetic semiconductors, the establishment of a conducting channel within the material is needed. So, FETs are well-suited for this purpose due to their ability to establish the conducting channel through electrostatic gating. However, it is yet uncommon to fabricate magnetic semiconductor FETs and do the in-plane transport measurements. In contrast, there have been extensive experimental study employing vertical transport experiments, such as in the family of chromium trihalides (CrX_3 , $\text{X}=\text{Cl}$, Br , I) [69][70], in CrSBr [71], and in MnPS_3 [72], etc.

This is because the realization of magnetic semiconductor field-effect transistors is challenging. The majority of 2D magnetic semiconductors are susceptible to chemical instability in ambient conditions [37], making the fabrication of electrodes on them very difficult. A more significant limitation is that many 2D magnetic semiconductors have very poor charge carrier mobility [35]. The low mobility severely affects the performance of FETs and can even make them dysfunctional, particularly at cryogenic temperatures. The poor mobility is attributed to their extremely narrow bandwidths, typically on the order of a few tens of meV or even lower [73][74]. As a result, conduction band electrons

in these materials exhibit a large effective mass, resulting in the localization of electrons [34][75] (Figure 2.11). With the very low charge carrier mobility, the conducting channel

Figure 2.11: Representative narrow bandwidths 2D magnetic semiconductors. (a) Band structure of trigonal CrCl_3 obtained from the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) calculations for the antiferromagnetic configurations [73]. (b) Band structures obtained from ab initio study for the bilayer-I phase of FePSe_3 , the energy at the top of the valence band is set as zero [74].

shows very small current that are easily disturbed by noise, limiting its ability to detecting materials' magnetic orders. For most investigated 2D magnets so far, either no transistor behavior was observed or the devices showed poor qualities and only operated above the critical temperature [35].

Figure 2.12: Three known large-bandwidth 2D van der Waals magnetic semiconductors. (a) The electronic band structure of monolayer CrSBr in its ferromagnetic ground state obtained from GW calculations, showing a semiconducting bandgap of approximately 1.8eV and pronounced anisotropic band dispersion.[76] (b) The electronic band structures of bilayer NiI_2 using DFT+U calculations [36]. (c) The electronic band structures of CrPS_4 at 298K obtained from DFT + DMFT calculation [77].

To date, there are only a limited number of FETs based on 2D magnetic semiconductors successfully fabricated and demonstrated to operate effectively at low temperatures.

So far, FETs based on three types of 2D magnetic semiconductors have been reported, namely CrSBr [34], CrPS₄ [35], and NiI₂ [37]. The reason why the above three materials exhibit larger mobilities compared to others is that all of them have large bandwidth. Specifically, CrSBr exhibits a bandwidth exceeding 1.5 eV [76], while CrPS₄ [77] and NiI₂ [36] display bandwidths around 1 eV (Figure 2.12).

The availability of FETs based on 2D magnetic semiconductors offer a unique opportunity to characterize the electronic and magnetic properties of 2D magnets, which is challenging to achieve with other methods. For example, researchers use NiI₂-based FETs to electrically probe the thickness-dependent multiferroic phase transition temperature of NiI₂ [37]. These NiI₂ FETs can operate properly down to 1.7 K. Figure 2.13.a shows

Figure 2.13: (a) The transfer curves of a bilayer NiI₂ FET measured at different temperatures ($V_{sd} = 2 V$), with the inset displaying the same data on a log-linear scale. (b) The resistance of different few-layer NiI₂ FETs plotted against temperature, revealing a decrease of Néel temperature in thicker samples [37].

the transfer curves of bilayer NiI₂ FETs measured at representative temperatures. From these transfer curves, it is seen clearly that source-drain current is dependent on temperature. Figure 2.13.b shows the resistance as a function of temperature for different thicknesses of NiI₂ FETs. Each R - T curve exhibits a distinct peak, whose positions vary with thickness. These peaks correspond to the helical magnetic and structural transition of NiI₂ [37], showing the thickness-dependent multiferroic phase transition temperature of NiI₂ from 59 K (bulk) to 28 K (monolayer) [37]. The absence of net magnetization in antiferromagnetic NiI₂ makes it challenging to detect its magnetic order using conventional magnetic-optical methods [37]. This experiment clearly shows the advantages of using magnetic semiconductor FETs to probe 2D magnetism, especially in the case of 2D antiferromagnetic materials. It is worth mentioning that researches utilized graphene as contacts for their NiI₂ FETs. They chose graphene rather than metal because they observed that direct deposition of metal contacts on NiI₂ FETs led to significantly lower mobility, around 100 times lower at low temperatures [37].

Another example is the CrSBr FETs. Researchers can conduct transport measurements along the in-plane a and b crystallographic directions, revealing the strong anisotropy in transport properties and even quasi-1D electronic transport behavior [34]. Figure 2.14.a and b show the transfer curves of 12- nm -thick CrSBr FETs measured along crystallo-

Figure 2.14: Transfer curves of CrSBr FETs in the a -direction (a) and in the b -direction (b) for different temperatures. Both CrSBr multilayers are 12- nm -thick. [34].

graphic a and b directions respectively. The FET behaviour is observed along a but the gate doesn't modulate the conductance along b . This phenomenon is highly interesting and has not been previously reported for any other semiconducting material [34]. The mechanism behind it still needs to be further explored.

In this thesis, we focus on CrPS₄ FETs. Previously, researchers were able to fabricate two-terminal CrPS₄ FETs that operated properly down to cryogenic temperatures. They were able to determine the complete magnetic phase diagram of CrPS₄, including both the spin-flop and spin-flip phase transitions [35], which is very difficult to complete with magneto-optical methods. Besides, they also observed unexpected large magnetoconductance, both near T_N and at low temperatures. They were able to determine two different microscopic mechanisms responsible for the large magnetoconductance at different temperature ranges [38]. Additionally, they also reported slightly gate-tuned magnetic phase boundary. In section 2.5, we will provide a detailed introduction to the above-mentioned experimental results of CrPS₄ FETs.

2.4 Gate control of magnetism in 2D materials

In the previous subsection, we discussed the utilization of magnetic semiconductor FETs to do in-plane transport measurements for the detection of 2D magnetism and the exploration of the interplay between magnetic and semiconducting properties, which is one of

the motivation for our study. In this section, we delve into another intriguing aspect of 2D materials, namely the gate control of 2D magnetism. As mentioned in section 2.2, 2D materials' properties can be easily controlled by external factors. Based on this fact, we anticipate to investigate the gate control of magnetism in this thesis using our magnetic semiconductor FETs. In short, these magnetic semiconductor FETs serve twofold purposes: on the one hand, they serve as detectors to probe the magnetic properties of 2D magnets, including parameters like Néel temperature and spin-flip/flop field, which was introduced in section 2.3; on the other hand, they allow us to actively manipulate the electric field and charge carrier density, thus potentially manipulating the magnetic properties, which is the topic of this section.

Traditionally, the electrical control of magnetism were mainly studied in the FETs based on thin films grown on substrates [78]. Around 20 years ago, researchers initially demonstrated the electrical manipulation of magnetic phase transition in magnetic semiconductor (In,Mn)As-based FETs [79]. The recently discovery of 2D van der Waals magnets offers a new platform for studying this interesting phenomenon [31][30][80][81][35]. Researchers discovered that electrostatic gating can lead to significant modifications in their magnetic properties, including the critical temperature [31], the critical field for magnetic phase transitions (such as spin-flip and spin-flop field) [35], the strength of exchange coupling and the magnetic ground state [30].

In FETs, the gate voltage has two different influence on the sample: it brings in an electric field, and it tunes the charge carrier density. The two parameters play different roles in different materials. For example, in multiferroics, there is an inherent coupling between magnetization and electrical polarization [78]. Therefore, changes in magnetization are primarily driven by the applied electric field rather than the carrier density [22]. Whereas in some magnetic semiconductors, the variations in charge carrier density have a significant impact on the magnetic exchange interaction and magnetic anisotropy, allowing for the tuning of magnetism [78]. For a single-gate FET, the application of the electric field also brings the change in doping level, making it very challenging to analyze their individual effects independently. This problem can be addressed by fabricating double-gate FETs. For example, Jiang et al. utilized double gate devices to separately study the two parameters' influence on bilayer CrI₃ [30][82]. In their experiments, magnetic circular dichroism was used to characterize the samples' net magnetization. A bilayer CrI₃ flake is touched by graphene electrodes and is encapsulated in hBN thin layers to exclude the influence from the environment. Additionally, it is sandwiched by two conducting graphene that serves as gates.

They found the electric field and charge carrier density have very different influence to the magnetic properties, with different mechanism. Firstly, they studied the effect of an electric field [82]. They started with measuring the MCD signal as a function of magnetic

field in the absence of an electric field, as depicted in Figure 2.15.a. The forward and

Figure 2.15: Electric-field-controlled magnetism in bilayer CrI₃. (a) The magneto-optical circular dichroism signal was measured as a function of magnetic field under representative electric fields at 4K. (b) Relative and absolute change in the net magnetization as a function of electric field under a fixed magnetic field of 0 T (open red and black symbols for systems prepared under 1 T and -1 T, respectively) and at 1 T (filled symbols). The broad lines represent linear fits to the data. [82]

backward sweeps of magnetic field shows a hysteresis, indicating the presence of two distinct AFM ground states that are time-inversion-related (see the insets of Figure 2.15.a) [82]. These different ground states could be prepared by initially raising the magnetic field to ± 1 T and then turning off the magnetic field. Then, they turned on the electric field, and observe that a larger electric field causes a larger deviation of net magnetization from zero (ΔM) in the AFM phase (Figure 2.15.c). What's more, the forward and backward sweeps of magnetic field show the opposite sign of deviation. The ΔM is summarized in Figure 2.15.b, where it is shown clearly that ΔM is linearly proportional to E , which is known as the linear magnetoelectric (ME) effect. For the two time-reversal related AFM phases, the sign of this linear ME effect is the opposite.

Instead, the study [30] revealed that large electron doping can change the ground state of bilayer CrI₃ from AFM to FM at zero fields. And this shift of ground state is due to the modification of interlayer exchange coupling. As shown in Figure 2.16.a, with the increase of total gate voltage (electron doping), the region of AFM phase shrinks until it disappears. Above the critical density, the bilayer CrI₃ is turned into a ferromagnetic material, which is characterized by the hysteresis loop of MCD. The complete phase

Figure 2.16: Doping-controlled interlayer magnetism in bilayer CrI_3 . (a) MCD signal as a function of the magnetic field at 4 K for different gate voltages. The spin-flip magnetic phase transition field decreases with increasing gate voltage (electron doping). (b) The magnetic phase diagram at 4 K. (c) The interlayer exchange coupling (black line) and the spin-flip transition field (blue line) as functions of the gate voltage. [30]

diagram is shown in Figure 2.16.b, which clearly demonstrates the influence of charge carrier density on the spin-flip magnetic phase transition field H_{flip} . Since the H_{flip} is related to the J_{\perp} , they were able to estimate J_{\perp} from H_{flip} (see 2.16.c). According to their estimation, at large charge carrier density, the sign of J_{\perp} is shifted from positive to negative, changing the ground state from AFM to FM (the sign convention in paper [30] is opposite to this thesis).

The aforementioned experiments testify that electric field and charge carrier density have fundamentally different mechanisms to control magnetic properties. And it is important to fabricate double-gate FETs to distinguish their influences. In this thesis, one of our objectives is also to investigate the electrical manipulation of magnetism. As will be discussed in detail in section 2.5, previous studies have already reported a certain degree of gate-controlled magnetism in single-gate CrPS_4 FETs [35]. We hope to explore whether the tunability of magnetism arises from the electric field or the charge carrier density. So, we proposed to fabricate double-gate CrPS_4 FETs, which will allow us to independently

control and analyze the effects of both factors and potentially give an accurate explanation of the origin of gate-controlled magnetism in CrPS₄.

2.5 Magnetic semiconductor CrPS₄

As mentioned before, transport measurements are accurate and sensitive methods to detect and study 2D magnetism, especially for antiferromagnetic materials with vanishing net magnetization. In this thesis, we study CrPS₄ FETs, because CrPS₄ has been reported to exhibit air-stability [83][84] and possesses a large bandwidth of approximately 1 eV [35]. To date, all CrPS₄-based FETs have been limited to two-terminal and single-gate devices with graphene as contacts. In this thesis, we aim to fabricate multiterminal and double-gate CrPS₄ FETs that are functional at cryogenic temperatures. In this section, we focus on introducing the known properties of CrPS₄.

2.5.1 Crystal structure, magnetic order, and electronic band structure

The crystal structure of bulk CrPS₄ were revealed by X-ray and electron diffraction [83], as shown in Figure 2.17. CrPS₄ has a monoclinic crystal structure with $a = 10.8\text{\AA}$, $b =$

Figure 2.17: Crystal structure of CrPS₄ [83].

7.3\AA , $c = 6.1\text{\AA}$, $\alpha = 90^\circ$, $\beta = 92^\circ$, and $\gamma = 90^\circ$ [85]. Since its β angle is very close to 90° , sometimes it can be viewed as an orthorhombic crystal for simplicity. High-quality CrPS₄ crystal can be prepared using chemical vapor transport (CVT) [83]. In Figure 2.17, it is depicted clearly that van der Waals material CrPS₄ has a layered structure: In each layer, chromium atoms situate in the middle of the sulfur octahedrons connected along the b-direction. These sulfur octahedrons are separated by the phosphorus atoms along the a-direction. Different layers are separated by a van der Waals gap along the c-direction, making it possible to be exfoliated down to thin layers using the traditional

micromechanical exfoliation method. In each layer, the lattice constant a is 48% larger than the lattice constant b .

Figure 2.18: (a) Diffraction patterns of CrPS₄ powder sample at 40 K and 1.7 K. (b) Zero-field-cooled magnetic susceptibilities of CrPS₄ single crystal. (c) Crystal and magnetic structure of CrPS₄ [29].

Neutron powder diffraction was applied to unravel the magnetic structure of bulk-formed CrPS₄ [29]. As shown in Figure 2.18.a, compared with the neutron diffraction patterns at $T = 40\text{ K}$, three new magnetic diffraction peaks are formed at $T = 1.7\text{ K}$. According to their analysis and calculation, these magnetic diffraction peaks are formed due to the formation of A-type antiferromagnetism (see Figure 2.18.c), which is purely a magnetic phase transition with the structure unchanged [29]. Another piece of evidence supporting the formation of antiferromagnetism is their zero-field-cooled magnetization characteristics measurement (see Figure 2.18.b). The magnetization curves reveal that the easy axis of CrPS₄ crystal is along the c -direction, which is in agreement with the NPD result. Also, the Néel temperature was extracted to be 38 K.

Atomically thin samples of CrPS₄ are relatively less studied. In 2021, the layer-dependent magnetization in CrPS₄, ranging from monolayer to five layers, was observed using magneto-optical Kerr effect microscopy [84]. This study confirmed that CrPS₄ keeps its magnetic properties down to atomically thin limit (Figure 2.19). In their work, researchers perform micromechanical exfoliation in the ambient environment to obtain thin layers of CrPS₄. Figure 2.19.a shows the optical image of CrPS₄ flakes ranging from 1 layer to 5 layers. They confirmed the layer number of each flake through atomic force microscopy and site-dependent Raman spectra (Figure 2.19.b). With the confirmation

Figure 2.19: layer-dependent magnetic properties of thin CrPS_4 flakes from 1L to 5L. (a) Microscope image of exfoliated CrPS_4 . The scale bar is $5 \mu\text{m}$ (b) Raman spectrum measured on 1L to 5L flakes as shown in the microscope image. (c) Temperature dependence of the MOKE signal under $\mu_0 H = 0.25 \text{ T}$ measured on the 1L to 5L flakes shown in the microscope image. (d) Raman peak intensity of the F peak for each flake (normalized by that from the 5L). (e) Critical temperature, T_c (black dashed bar), and critical exponent, β (blue symbol), extracted from the fitting lines shown in panel c. [84]

of layer number, the magnetic properties are investigated through magneto-optical Kerr effect microscopy at different temperatures. In 2L and 4L (even layer number) flakes, the Kerr rotation angle (θ_{KR}) is vanishingly small within the temperature range studied, similar to the behavior observed in bulk samples. Interestingly, in 1L, 3L, and 5L (odd layer number) flakes of CrPS_4 , non-zero values of θ_{KR} are detected at temperatures below 23 K (Figure 2.19.c), which means a non-zero net magnetization [84]. The alternating zero and non-zero net magnetization observed in even and odd layers implies the presence of A-type antiferromagnetism in atomically thin CrPS_4 . Besides, the study confirms a reduction in the Néel temperature and the air-stable property of the thin CrPS_4 flakes.

In 2023, A. R. Alcantara, et al. employed the recently developed Strongly-Constrained-and-Appropriately-Normed (SCAN) meta-GGA density functional to calculate the spin-dependent transport properties of CrPS_4 from bulk to monolayer [86]. The spin-resolved electronic band structures of CrPS_4 are shown in Figure 2.20. The calculation result clearly shows that CrPS_4 has a band gap of $\sim 1.34 \text{ eV}$, which is in very good agreement with the optical experimental result of $\sim 1.35 \text{ eV}$ [87]. This band gap is not so wide. Another observation is that the conduction band has a relatively large bandwidth of $\sim 0.75 \text{ eV}$ (Figure 2.20.a and d). There are other calculations based on density functional theory coupled with the nonequilibrium Green's function formalism [88] showing the band gap reaches $\sim 1 \text{ eV}$. Compared with most 2D magnetic semiconductors whose bandwidths are $\sim 0.1 \text{ eV}$ [35], CrPS_4 has significantly larger bandwidths. It is worth noting that for monolayer CrPS_4 , the electronic bands are spin-resolved due to the ferro-

Figure 2.20: (a) The calculated electronic band structure for the bulk, bilayer, and trilayer CrPS₄. The inset shows the explored Brillouin zone route. (b) The total and atomically resolved density of states for the bulk. (c) The total and atomically resolved density of states for the monolayer. (d) Monolayer band structure with spin-up (red) and spin-down (green) bands. [86]

magnetic nature of monolayer CrPS₄, which indicates the correlation between magnetic states and semiconducting behavior, as will be introduced in detail in section 2.5.

2.5.2 Bulk H-T magnetic phase diagram

The magnetic phase as a function of temperature is already discussed in Figure 2.2: below the critical temperature T_c , magnetic orders emerge (FM or AFM). Actually, the application of an external magnetic field can induce new magnetic phases, known as metamagnetic phases. Researchers determined the complete magnetic phase diagram of bulk CrPS₄ when the magnetic field is applied parallel to the c-axis from complementary neutron diffraction, magnetic, and torque measurements [29], which is shown in Figure 2.21. The magnetic phase diagram is divided into four distinct regions: 1. The paramagnetic phase above the Néel temperature $T_N = 38$ K, where the CrPS₄ does not exhibit any long-range magnetic order; 2. The A-type antiferromagnetic ground state in low magnetic fields (< 0.7 T) below T_N ; 3. The canted antiferromagnetic (CAFM) phase, where the magnetic moments are aligned antiferromagnetically along the b-axis but possess a small angle relative to the *ab*-plane (Figure 2.21); 4. The ferromagnetic-like phase at high magnetic fields that are sufficient to overcome the antiferromagnetic exchange coupling (> 8 T), where all the magnetic moments align parallel to the applied magnetic field.

The four magnetic phases host two metamagnetic transitions. At 1.7 K, a spin-flop transition takes place at approximately 0.7 T, and a spin-flip phase transition takes place at 8 T. The spin-flip field and the spin-flop field shift to smaller values as temperature increases. As we know, spin-flop usually occurs when the magnetocrystalline anisotropy is relatively weak, while spin-flip transitions are typically observed in materials with strong magnetocrystalline anisotropy [89][90]. Here in CrPS₄, the observed metamagnetic tran-

Figure 2.21: Magnetic phase diagram of bulk CrPS₄ crystal obtained from complementary neutron diffraction, DC magnetization and cantilever-based torque measurements [29].

sition fields are small compared to other known A-type van der Waals antiferromagnetic materials, indicating the weak interlayer coupling between neighboring layers and the low magnetic anisotropy energy [29].

So far, spin-flop transitions have been experimentally observed in a wide range of antiferromagnetic systems including conventional antiferromagnets like CuCl₂ · 2H₂O [91] and NiO [92], in antiferromagnetic topological insulator MnBi₂Te₄ [93], and in antiferromagnetic van der Waals materials like MPS₃ ($M = \text{Ni}$ and Mn) [94]. However, the spin-flop transition is difficult to observe with magneto-optical methods [35], because the sample exhibits nearly vanishing net magnetization before and immediately after the phase transition.

2.5.3 In-plane magneto-transport properties of multilayer CrPS₄

To date, there have been very few experimental transport studies both on bulk form and on atomically thin layers of CrPS₄. In this section, we focus on the introduction of very recently reported in-plane transport properties of multilayer CrPS₄ by Wu et al. [35]. They successfully fabricated the CrPS₄ FETs that perform well at the lowest temperature of $T = 250$ mK. This allows them to investigate the magneto-transport properties over a

wide temperature range. The schematic diagram of their CrPS₄ FETs is shown in Figure 2.22.a, where a 10-nm-thick CrPS₄ multilayer is encapsulated between two layers of hBN, with graphite serving as the two electrodes, and a silicon bottom gate is used. They first

Figure 2.22: The transport properties of CrPS₄ FETs at different temperatures. (a) Transfer curves of CrPS₄ FETs at representative temperatures. (b) Low-temperature output curves measured at $V_G = 80$ V at selected temperatures. (c) The conductance as a function of temperature measured at source-drain bias $V_{SD} = 2$ V at different fixed V_G values. [35]

did some basic characterization to their CrPS₄ FETs. As shown in Figure 2.22.d, clear transfer curves are observed, where the threshold voltages shift to higher values at lower temperatures, which is consistent with the behavior of doped semiconductors. However, the conductance is very low, which might come from the contact resistance. As shown in Figure 2.22.b, the output curves show pronounced non-linearity at low temperatures, indicating the presence of the Schottky barrier. In Figure 2.22.c, the conductance is plotted as a function of temperature. As the temperature decreases, as expected, the conductance initially decreases. Surprisingly, an increase in conductance is observed around the Néel temperature. This conductance increase was attributed to the onset of long-range spin ordering, which suppresses the disorder associated with spin fluctuations within each CrPS₄ layer [35]. This phenomenon will be further explained in Section 2.5.4. The Néel temperatures are determined by locating the minimum of the dG/dT curves, which are around 35 K. These values are slightly lower than the reported Néel temperature of 38 K for bulk samples [29].

They also discovered that CrPS₄ FETs show very large magnetoconductance, which is an unexpected phenomenon not observed in CrSBr and NiI₂ transistors. Figure 2.23.a

Figure 2.23: (a) Magnetoconductance measured at $V_G = 80$ V, $V_{sd} = 2$ V at indicated temperatures. The magnetic field is applied perpendicular to the ab -plane of CrPS₄. (b) Zoom-in of the magnetoconductance in the magnetic field ranging from -1 to 1 T. (c) The color plot of dG/dH as a function of temperature and magnetic field.

shows the magnetoconductance measured at $V_G = 80$ V and $V_{sd} = 2$ V. The magnetoconductance is large both around T_N and far below T_N . Right now, there is no established mechanism suggesting such large magnetoconductance in CrPS₄ FETs for $T < T_N$ [35]. So, the study of the mechanism behind it is very interesting, which is a topic of Section 2.5.4. The measurement of magnetoconductance also allows researchers to explore the relationship between magnetoconductance and magnetic state. For example, Figure 2.23.b shows the magnetoconductance in the zoom-in range from -1 to 1 T, where clear kinks were observed for the temperatures below T_N . These kinks happen at around ± 0.6 T, which closely matches the spin-flop field of 0.7 T obtained from NPD results [29]. Besides, as seen from Figure 2.23.a, the magnetoconductance stops increasing rapidly above approximately 8 T, which also agrees with earlier NPD results [29]. Knowing the coupling between magnetoconductance and magnetic state, researchers determined the full magnetic phase diagram of multilayer CrPS₄ (Figure 2.23.c) simply by measuring the

magnetoconductance at different temperatures, which is very difficult to accomplish with other methods in atomically thin layers. For example, the spin-flop transition has not been detected in any exfoliated 2D magnet by means of magneto-optics experiments. [35]

However, as previously mentioned, their work only reported the measurements performed on graphene-contact 2-terminal devices, which limited their ability to comprehensively analyze the scale and influence of contact resistance and the graphene contacts. There are still open questions to answer. For example, the presence of contact resistance might introduce inaccuracy and even errors in determining the values of H_{flip} , H_{flop} , and T_N . On the other hand, it's well known that graphene itself exhibits large magnetoconductance. Whether the graphene contacts contributed to the measured large magnetoconductance is unknown. This thesis aims to address these open questions by fabricating multiterminal CrPS₄ FETs and conducting comprehensive magneto-transport measurements to provide insights and clarity on these problems.

2.5.4 Mechanisms responsible for the large magnetoconductance in CrPS₄ FETs

In order to understand the mechanism behind the large magnetoconductance introduced in the previous section, researchers conducted a thorough analysis of important FET parameters, including the carrier mobility (μ) and threshold voltage (V_{th}), as a function of temperature and magnetic field [38]. These parameters provide crucial intrinsic information about the material. For instance, the V_{th} is determined by the energy difference between the Fermi level and the conduction band edge (E_g), as well as other factors such as trapped charges. When all other factors such as doping level, device geometry, and impurities remain constant, a shift in the V_{th} can indicate a shift in the conduction band edge. Experimentally, the V_{th} is obtained by extrapolating the tangent line of the transfer curves at the maximum first derivative (slope) [95]. On the other hand, the carrier mobility characterizes how quickly a charge carrier drifts under an external electric field, which can be described by the Drude model $v_d = \mu E$. Mobility serves as an indicator of material quality, as it is influenced by factors such as material defects, impurities, and various scattering mechanisms. Higher mobility suggests weaker scattering processes and a suppression of disorder, whereas lower mobility indicates stronger scattering and a higher degree of disorder in the device. Experimentally, the extraction of μ starts with the formula describing the current in the FETs:

$$I = \frac{W}{L} \mu c (V_G - V_{th}) V_{SD} \quad (2.4)$$

, where W and L are the width and length of the channel separately, and c stands for the capacitance per unit area. By combining the Drude model and the above equation, μ can

be extracted from the linear part of the transfer curve:

$$\mu = \frac{1}{ec} \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial V_G} \quad (2.5)$$

Analyzing these parameters can help researchers determine the microscopic mechanism for the behavior of conductance. For example, in the study [38], researchers firstly examined the transfer curves of CrPS₄ FETs over a temperature range from 60 K to 2 K, as depicted in Figure 2.24.a. The threshold voltage exhibits a gradual increase of approxi-

Figure 2.24: (a) Transfer curves of a FET based on 10-*nm*-thick CrPS₄ multilayer, measured at indicated temperatures. (b) The temperature dependence of the mobility extracted from the transfer curves at a gate voltage of 100 V, showing a fourfold increase as the temperature is lowered below T_N . (c) The temperature dependence of the threshold voltage, obtained by extrapolating the linear part of transfer curves. [35]

mately 10 V as the temperature is lowered from 60 K to 2 K (Figure 2.24.c). On the other hand, the mobility increases by a factor of 4 below Néel temperature, and eventually saturates at low temperatures [38]. The up-shift of V_G can be understood by the electrons becoming frozen within the dopants in CrPS₄ upon cooling down [38]. The large increase in mobility around T_N confirms the strong correlation between conductance and magnetic order. In the vicinity of T_N , magnetic long-range order is not well established, resulting in strong spin fluctuations. The cooling process reduces the disorder originating from spin fluctuations, thus increasing the material's mobility. At low temperatures ($T \ll T_N$), the magnetic order is fully established, so the mobility saturates. This mechanism explains the aforementioned unexpected increase of conductance around T_N shown in Figure 2.22.c.

Figure 2.25: (a) Magnetoconductance curves measured at different temperatures. Large magnetoconductance is observed at 38 K (around T_N). (b) Near T_N ($T = 30, 40, 50$ K), the mobility extracted from the transfer curves as a function of magnetic field, showing a 5-10 times increase at 10 T compared with zero field. (c) Near T_N , the threshold voltage obtained by extrapolating the linear part of transfer curves, showing a minor shift of 10%. [35][38]

Using the similar analysis method, the researchers also investigated the large magnetoconductance observed near T_N , as depicted in Figure 2.25.a. They measured the transfer curves at temperatures of 30 K, 40 K, and 50 K, and at the magnetic field ranging from 0 to 10 T. From these transfer curves, they extracted the mobility and threshold voltage, which are summarized in Figure 2.25.b and c, respectively. As the magnetic field is increased from 0 to 10 T, the mobility undergoes a significant increase of 5-10 times. In contrast, the threshold voltage shows only a modest increase of 10%. So, the large magnetoconductance is attributed to the increase in μ [38]. This phenomenon is also comprehensible with the mechanism of spin fluctuations: around T_N , the magnetic susceptibility is large (see Figure 2.2), making the application of a magnetic field highly effective in suppressing spin fluctuations, leading to an increase in the carrier mobility, thus exhibiting a large magnetoconductance.

However, even at very low temperatures, such as 2 K, CrPS₄ FETs continue to exhibit a large magnetoconductance (see Figure 2.25.a). This observation is intriguing because at such temperatures, the magnetic order is well-established. The minimal spin fluctuations suggest that they are not the cause of the large magnetoconductance. To investigate this phenomenon, the researchers analyzed the transfer curves at 2 K under magnetic fields ranging from 0 to 10 T. (Figure 2.26.a).

Figure 2.26: (a) Transfer curves of CrPS₄ FETs measured at 2 K at magnetic field ranging from 0 to 10 T (b) All the transfer curves measured in (a) can collapse well with each other after shifting by their respective threshold voltage. (c) Threshold voltage and mobility extracted from the transfer curves shown in (a). The mobility remains unchanged while the threshold voltage shift downwards by 30 V when magnetic field is increased from 0 to 10 T. [38]

Figure 2.27: First-principles calculations of the band structure of bilayer CrPS₄ in the AFM and FM states. The blue and red colors represent the spin-up and spin-down states respectively. The conduction band edge in the FM phase is calculated to be 33 meV lower than in the AFM phase. [38]

These curves can collapse on top of each other when shifted by their respective threshold voltages (Figure 2.26.b), indicating that μ remains unaffected by the applied magnetic field. Therefore, the large magnetoconductance can only be attributed to the shift in threshold voltages (Figure 2.26.c). As mentioned previously, the shift in threshold volt-

ages indicates the shift of the conduction band edge when other factors remain unchanged. Through their estimation, the downward shift of 30 V in the threshold voltage corresponds to the downshift of the conduction band of $\Delta E \approx 15 \text{ meV}$ [38]. This value compares well with the calculated conduction band downshift of 33 meV when the CrPS₄ transits from an AFM state to a FM state (Figure 2.27).

The aforementioned study proves that FETs are indeed very good platforms to study the intricate interplay between the magnetic state and the semiconducting properties of magnetic semiconductors. They were able to find out the microscopic mechanism responsible for the large magnetoconductance by extracting important parameters like V_{th} and μ from transfer curves. However, these measurements share the same problems pointed out in the previous section: the contact resistance between graphene and CrPS₄ is unknown. As we know, non-Ohmic contact resistance, such as Schottky contacts, typically exhibit temperature and V_{sd} dependence [96]. Moreover, graphene resistance strongly depends on the magnetic field. Directly comparing transfer curves under different temperatures and magnetic fields overlooks the possible changes in contact resistance and probe resistance. Employing 4-terminal measurements could effectively address this problem. However, until now, the study of multiterminal CrPS₄ FETs has never been performed, despite their significant importance. The main challenge lies in establishing the electrical contacts on CrPS₄, for which we managed to find a proper solution as described in the next chapter.

2.5.5 Gate-tuned magnetism in multilayer CrPS₄

Researchers also reported the gate-controlled magnetic phenomenon in their CrPS₄ FETs [35]. Figure 2.28.a shows the magnetoconductance measured at 2 K at different gate voltages ranging from 50 V to 85 V, where it is clearly observed that the spin-flip field is gate-tunable. Figure 2.28.b shows the magnetoconductance measured from another device based on a 10 nm CrPS₄ multilayer at similar conditions, which demonstrates that this phenomenon is repeatable. Researchers summarized the shift of magnetic phase transition fields as a function of V_G in Figure 2.28.c. When the gate voltage is increased from 50 V to 80 V, the spin-flip field decreases by 0.3 T, while the spin-flop field increases by 20 mT. The modification of H_{flip} and H_{flop} by gate suggests that the gate can influence both the exchange interaction and the magnetic anisotropy [35]. Although the effect of gate-tuned magnetism in CrPS₄ is small, other realized magnetic semiconductor FETs, namely CrSBr and CrI₂, have not shown any modulation of magnetism with varying gate voltage [35].

The gate-controlled magnetism in CrPS₄ FETs is also a very interesting topic that we would like to further study. Knowing whether this tunability arises from the electric field or the charge carrier density will be very helpful to study the exact mechanism responsible for such gate-tuned magnetism. So, we proposed to fabricate double-gate devices

Figure 2.28: (a) The measured magnetoconductance curves exhibit clear dependence on gate voltage ranging from 50 V to 85 V. The inset shows the derivative of the magnetoconductance. (b) The magnetoconductance curves for another device based on a 10 nm CrPS₄ multilayer at similar conditions. (c) The spin-flip (open green symbols) and spin-flop (open orange symbols) fields as a function of gate voltage summarized from transport measurements. [35]

to independently control the electric field and charge carrier density. Moreover, the observed gate tunability is not significant, which may be attributed to the thick CrPS₄ flakes (around 10-nm). The gate primarily affects the first one or two layers of CrPS₄ near the surface. So, finding a CrPS₄ flake as thin as possible may help us to get a more significant signal. The details of device fabrication and experimental techniques are presented in the next Chapter.

Chapter 3

Device fabrication and experimental techniques

3.1 Fabrication of multiterminal CrPS₄ device

In the thesis, we aim to fabricate double-gate multiterminal CrPS₄ FETs that are functional even at cryogenic temperatures. The selection of contact geometry, and contact material should be done with careful consideration.

Top contact and edge contact are two common types of contact geometries used for 2D materials [97]. On the other hand, bottom contacts, while not as commonly used as top contacts, are still a popular choice and are likely employed as frequently as edge contacts. The top contact geometry can be easily constructed by depositing metals directly on top of 2D materials, while the 1D edge contact method involves etching the entire stack to expose the edge of the magnetic semiconductor, followed by depositing metal for contact. However, for magnetic semiconductor CrPS₄, we tried top contact and proved that top contact did not work. As for the 1D edge contact, although it is highly successful for graphene [98], it only achieved limited success for other 2D materials until now [99][100]. Therefore, in this thesis, we explore alternative methods before trying the 1D edge contact.

After careful consideration, we finally adapted the bottom contact geometry in this thesis. The bottom contact involved initially fabricating hall-shaped contacts, followed by aligning and transferring the CrPS₄ layer onto the contacts. This approach offers two main advantages. Firstly, it allows for encapsulation of the device entirely within the glove box, minimizing the exposure of CrPS₄ to the ambient environments, thus preserving its properties. Secondly, it eliminates the need for etching of CrPS₄, as we want to avoid any potential modifications in the material's properties that may arise from etching processes.

After deciding on the geometry, we explored the materials that contact with CrPS₄. In total, we explored three different types of materials: multilayer graphene, gold, and platinum. Our initial choice was multilayer graphene, considering its successful application in fabricating NiI₂ FETs and two-terminal CrPS₄ FETs, as mentioned previously. A large multilayer graphene flake was initially exfoliated and patterned into Hall bars. Subsequently, a suitable CrPS₄ flake was transferred onto the graphene Hall bars. Figure 3.1.a presents a microscopic image of one of our fabricated graphene-contact CrPS₄ FETs. But

Figure 3.1: (a) A CrPS₄ FET device with pre-patterned multilayer graphene as bottom contacts prepared by chemical etching in an oxygen plasma. (b) A CrPS₄ FET device with gold as bottom contacts prepared by electron-beam lithography (EBL) and electron-beam evaporation.

unfortunately, all the realized graphene-contact CrPS₄ FETs don't exhibit FET characteristics (see Figure 4.1.a for the transfer curve of the device shown in Figure 3.1.a). One possible explanation for this outcome is the contamination of the graphene by organic residuals during the nano-fabrication processes. To address this issue, various cleaning methods were employed, such as deep UV cleaning and annealing. However, the FETs continued to malfunction, and organic residuals were still observed on the surface of the graphene contacts.

Subsequently, we attempted to use gold. The microscopic image of the gold-contacted CrPS₄ FETs is presented in Figure 3.1.b. As will be shown in Chapter 4, it was confirmed that gold can establish contact with CrPS₄. These FETs demonstrated tunability with both top and bottom gates at room temperature. But the current flowing through the devices was very small. As we cooled the system, the current gradually decreased until it became smaller than the noise level at cryogenic temperature. One potential explanation is that gold films with nanometer thickness have a tendency to form islands instead of homogeneous films [101][102]. Consequently, the CrPS₄ layer may only effectively contact with some of these gold islands (because some of them are disconnected from the electrode),

leading to a significantly reduced contact area and much larger contact resistance.

We ultimately selected platinum as the material for the bottom contact, which proved to be successful. The detailed processes of device fabrication will be thoroughly discussed in the subsequent sections.

3.1.1 Overview of device fabrication processes

In order to fabricate CrPS₄ FETs, three layers of van der Waals materials are needed (Figure 3.2): a thin layer of CrPS₄ crystal encapsulated by two layers of hBN. As mentioned

Figure 3.2: (a) Schematic diagram of CrPS₄-based field effect transistor device. (b) Optical microscopic image of the device

in section 2.4, double-gate devices are desired. So, these hBN layers also act as the dielectric materials for the gates. The details regarding the heterostructure assembly of the three layers can be found in section 3.1.2. Note that the bottom hBN is pre-patterned with 2 nm thick titanium and 5 nm thick platinum contacts arranged in a Hall-shaped geometry (details can be found in section 3.1.3) to make contact with CrPS₄ thin crystal, as outlined earlier in this chapter. The hBN layers are exfoliated in an ambient environment. Although CrPS₄ is reported to be air-stable, the CrPS₄ used in our device is exfoliated in a glove box, where O₂ and H₂O are maintained at a very low level (less than 1 ppm).

As shown in Figure 3.3, the fabrication process can be divided into two parts. Section 3.1.2 provides a comprehensive description of the first part of fabrication: heterostructure assembly. This section covers the processes including the exfoliation of hBN and CrPS₄ thin crystals, the fabrication of stamps, the picking up techniques, the alignment of CrPS₄ crystal to the pre-patterned bottom hBN, and the release of the CrPS₄ crystal from the stamp. The second part is about contact deposition including electron beam lithography and electron beam evaporation, which is the standard nano-fabrication process used to fabricate devices based on exfoliated 2D materials. An in-depth description of this part of

Figure 3.3: Overview of device fabrication processes. The whole fabrication process can be divided into two parts. The first part: heterostructure assembly is completed inside the glove box (as indicated by red dashed line). The second part is the standard contact deposition procedures inside clean room.

fabrication is presented in Section 3.1.3.

3.1.2 Atomically thin layers exfoliation and heterostructure assembly

Figure 3.4: (a) SEM image of the CrPS₄ single crystal employed in the EDS analysis. Elemental mapping of (b) Cr, (c) P, and (d) S, resulting in an atomic ratio $Cr : P : S$ of 16.92 : 16.60 : 66.48 [35].

The CrPS₄ single crystals used in our experiment to exfoliate CrPS₄ thin crystals were purchased from HQ Graphene. In order to confirm the crystal is indeed CrPS₄, we performed dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) to confirm its chemical composition.

Figure 3.5: Exfoliation process. (a) The bulk CrPS₄ crystal purchased from HQ Graphene. (b) A piece of CrPS₄ bulk crystal is put on a Scotch tape. (c) A new Scotch tape is employed to peel the CrPS₄ crystal into thinner pieces. (d) Thin CrPS₄ crystals are pressed onto a Si-SiO₂ substrate. A soft rubber is used to gently rub the tape before peeling it off. (e) The optical microscope image of exfoliated flakes. Statistically they mostly exhibit two crystal angles, namely 67° and 113°, which corresponds to the angles between two $\langle 110 \rangle$ axes of CrPS₄. (f) Microscope image of a thin CrPS₄ flake that exhibits light purple optical contrast.

As shown in the elements mapping results (Figure 3.4), the Cr, P, and S elements are uniformly distributed with an atomic ratio of 16.92 : 16.60 : 66.48. This ratio closely matches the expected stoichiometry of 1 : 1 : 4 [35].

After confirming the uniformity and elemental composition of CrPS₄ crystal, we followed the standard micromechanical exfoliation procedures to produce CrPS₄ thin layers rapidly, as shown in Figure 3.5. The purchased CrPS₄ crystal is first put on top of the adhesive tape (Figure 3.5.b). Then, a series of cleaving (exfoliation) processes were performed using another adhesive tape. This allowed for the thinning down of the bulk crystal and the generation of additional crystals (Figure 3.5.c). When the crystals on the tape start to lose metallic luster and turn gray, the desired thickness is achieved. Then, the adhesive tape, with the crystals on it, is carefully pressed onto a Si-SiO₂ substrate. When the tape, covered with bulk crystals, is peeled off from the substrate, the adhesive force between the bottom layer of the bulk crystal and the substrate can be larger than the van der Waals forces between the crystal layers. As a result, thin flakes are exfoliated onto the substrate. Based on our experience, the exfoliation process can yield a random number, area, and thickness of the exfoliated layers. However, there are methods to improve the chances of obtaining ultra-thin and isolated flakes. One such method is to use a soft rubber material to gently rub the tape before peeling it off (Figure 3.5.d). This helps increase the adhesion between the crystal and substrate. After removing the tape from the substrate, we examine the substrate using optical microscopy. We observe exfoliated crystals with varying optical contrast, indicating differences in their thickness (Figure 3.5.e). Interestingly, we also notice that the exfoliated flakes exhibit two distinct crystallographic angles, namely 67° and 113° (dashed white line in Figure 3.5.e and f), which are the values of the angles between two $\langle 110 \rangle$ axes of CrPS₄ [103][83]. In this thesis, the thinnest CrPS₄ crystals exhibit a light purple optical contrast, as shown in Figure 3.5.f. To ensure successful measurements, it is crucial to carefully select CrPS₄ flakes that are compatible with our pre-patterned contacts. The exfoliation of hBN follow similar procedures as CrPS₄, but is out side the glove box at ambient environment because hBN is very stable.

After exfoliating and isolating the desired CrPS₄ and hBN flakes, it is necessary to manipulate the positions of atomically thin layers and stack them on top of each other. This process, known as transfer, allows for the aligning and stacking of different 2D van der Waals materials. There are various transfer methods available nowadays. Among them, dry transfer methods have gained preference because dry transfer does not involve the use of etchants or liquid-based delamination processes [104]. In this thesis, we employed the dry transfer method.

The process starts by preparing a polycarbonate (PC) solution by dissolving PC granules in chloroform with a proportion of 1 g : 20 ml. The solution is then spin-coated onto a glass plate to form a film. To deposit the PC film onto a PDMS stamp positioned on a

glass plate, an adhesive tape with a pre-cut window is employed. This tape is used to peel off the PC film from its original glass plate and carefully stick it onto the PDMS stamp. Finally, the assembled stamp is baked at a temperature of 100°C for two minutes. After that, the stamp is ready for use.

The home-made transfer system used in this thesis is shown in Figure 3.6. This system

Figure 3.6: (a) The home-made transfer stage used to align and stack different 2D materials together. (b) The nitrogen-regulated glove box used to isolate the environment from the surrounding atmosphere in order to protect devices. (c) 3D schematic diagram of the device fabrication process inside the glove box. (d) A semi-finished bottom-contact device that is stacked entirely inside the glove box to maximize its properties.

includes an optical microscope, an X-Y-Z- θ stage (stage B) with a temperature control system for the substrate, another X-Y-Z stage (stage A) for the glass plate, and an auxiliary camera beside the stage B (Figure 3.6.a). The whole transfer system is put in the N_2 environment of the glove box to protect some air-sensitive 2D materials from degradation (Figure 3.6.b). A damping layer is added between the glove box and the ground to eliminate vibration as much as possible. These components allow for very precise positioning ($1\ \mu\text{m}$) of the PC stamps as well as the substrate, ensuring accurate alignment and control throughout the pick up and transfer process.

To fabricate CrPS₄ field-effect transistors, we followed the sequential pick-up process.

Initially, a stamp was fixed on stage A and positioned above the hBN substrate on stage B. The stamp was then brought into contact with the hBN substrate at a temperature of 90°C. The temperature was subsequently raised to 120°C and then cooled back down to 90°C to enhance the adhesion between the stamp and hBN. The stamp was then lifted, and the hBN flake was successfully picked up. Next, the stamp, now with the hBN flake on it, was aligned with the desired CrPS₄ flake under the microscope. The stamp was brought into contact with the CrPS₄ substrate at 120°C. After heating it up to 140°C and then cooling it back down to 120°C, the stamp was lifted, successfully picking up the CrPS₄ flake. Once the hBN and CrPS₄ are successfully picked up, they were carefully aligned and put into contact with the pre-patterned bottom contacts. Subsequently, the temperature of the substrate is raised to 180°C, causing the melt and release of the PC, hBN, and CrPS₄ onto the substrate. To remove the remaining PC layer, the substrate of the device is submerged in chloroform overnight. The resulting device is shown in Figure 3.6.d. For this particular device, some of the bottom contacts appear to be broken, indicating unintentional force between the stamp and substrate during the transfer process. This issue can be easily fixed as all the breakpoints are located on the bottom hBN layer, and are not covered by the top hBN layer. We just need to perform another step of EBL and electron-beam evaporation to deposit contacts that can fully cover these breakpoints, which will be introduced in the following section.

3.1.3 Contact fabrication

To perform electrical measurements on our devices, it is crucial to fabricate contacts on the thin 2D flakes, allowing for the connection with external electronic equipment. The fabrication procedures and contact geometries are customized to suit the specific device structures and research purpose. In this section, we describe the processes used to fabricate the bottom Pt contacts and the metal leads used to connect the device to the instruments used during the measurements.

In our laboratory, we utilize EBL as it is a versatile and powerful technique that enables us to fabricate contacts with a wide range of shapes and sizes. The EBL system in our lab is the state-of-the-art RAITH PIONEER Two. An oversimplified way to understand an EBL system is by viewing it as having three fundamental components: an electron source, an electromagnetic lens system, and a beam deflector. The electrons are emitted from a modern highest-brightness thermal field emission source. Once emitted, the electron beam passes through an electromagnetic lens system, which is capable of focusing the beam to an extremely small spot size of 1.6 nm. After that, a beam deflector is utilized to deflect the electron beam's path. After uploading our contact designs into the EBL control software and performing the necessary calibrations, it will automatically control the deflection of the electron beam, ensuring its precise arrival at the designated locations to form the desired pattern.

Figure 3.7: Schematic diagrams of the EBL process. (a) Two layers of PMMA are spin-coated on the substrate, which is later exposed to the controlled electron beam. (b) The undercut is formed due to two layers of PMMAs’ different sensitivity to the electron beam. (c) The deposited metal contacts on the substrate after the lift-off procedure in the acetone. (d) Metal is deposited on the substrate in an electron beam evaporator.

Figure 3.7 provides a simplified representation of the contact fabrication process. It involves the utilization of electron beam resists (E-beam resists) that are sensitive to electrons. For a positive E-beam resist, the regions exposed to the electron beam can be subsequently removed by the developer solution, which is known as the process of development. In this thesis, polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) is used as the positive E-beam resist. Firstly, the substrate is spin-coated with two layers of PMMA, with the molecular weights gradually increasing (the first layer is 50 K and the second layer is 950 K). Following that, electrons are exposed on the substrate according to the patterns that we designed (Figure 3.7.a). Later, the substrate is submerged in cold IPA/water with a ratio of 3 to 1. The utilization of double-layer PMMA aims to form the undercut, as illustrated in Figure 3.7.b. Subsequently, a deposition process is carried out using an electron-beam evaporator to cover the entire substrate with metal (Figure 3.7.c). The remaining PMMA is then removed through a lift-off procedure in the acetone. As a result, only the areas of the substrate/heterostructure where the PMMA was removed by the lithography process are covered by the metal (Figure 3.7.d), which are the desired contacts. The microscopic picture of the final device is shown in Figure 3.2.b.

Each CrPS₄ field-effect transistor requires two rounds of contact fabrication. In the first round, pre-patterned bottom contacts are created on top of the hBN. These bottom con-

tacts consist of 2 *nm* Ti and 5 *nm* Pt. These bottom contacts directly touch the CrPS₄ flake as a result of the heterostructure assembly. In the second round, the contact fabrication process not only creates the leads that connect to the contacts but also creates the top gate electrode (Figure 3.2.b).

After the contact fabrication, the final step is bonding wires on the device in preparation for the subsequent electronic transport measurements. As depicted in Figure 3.8, one end of the gold wire is bonded to the leads on the device using silver epoxy. On the other end, the wire is connected to the chip carrier. In our lab, the silver epoxy is a mixture of CircuitWorks Conductive Epoxy part A (epoxy) and part B (hardener). It solidifies after being heated at a temperature of 100°C for 30 minutes. The chip carrier is designed to fit with our measurement systems. Through the pins, connections are established with external electronic equipment, which are introduced in detail in the subsequent section.

Figure 3.8: (a) The commercial chip holder used in this thesis. (b) The device after wire bonding, which is ready for subsequent transport measurements.

3.2 Transport measurements

In order to do magneto-transport measurements, we employed many measurement systems and electronic equipment, which we will mention in this section.

The chip carrier (with bonded device) was firstly mounted onto a sample probe, which is then loaded inside the variable temperature insert (VTI) of the TeslatronPT cryogen-free system (Oxford Instrument). The VTI is surrounded by a 12 *T* vertical field superconducting solenoid magnet. This system allows the full control of sample temperature from 1.38 *K* to 300 *K*, while applying a controlled magnetic field produced by the integrated magnet.

The circuit diagram of the standard DC four-terminal methods is shown in Figure 3.9. A homemade low-noise source was utilized for applying the bias voltage V_{ds} . Two Keithley

Figure 3.9: (a) The microscopic image of a CrPS₄ FET device used to perform transport measurements in Chapter 4, which is accompanied by a circuit diagram illustrating the measurement configuration. (b) The schematic diagram of the CrPS₄ FET device along with a circuit diagram depicting the measurement setup.

2400 source/measure units were employed to apply the top gate voltage V_{TG} and bottom gate voltage V_{BG} and monitor the leakage current simultaneously. The current and voltage signals were amplified using homemade low-noise electronics, and two digital multimeters (Agilent 3410) were used to record the longitudinal voltage V_{xx} and source-drain current I_{ds} separately. All the above instruments were controlled using customized Labview programs, allowing for precise control and accurate measurement of the electrical properties of our devices.

Chapter 4

Experimental results

4.1 4-probe characterization to CrPS₄ FETs at room temperature

As discussed in Chapter 2, previous studies on CrPS₄ FETs were limited to two-terminal devices, and they exhibited significant contact resistance as indicated by highly non-linear I - V curves at low temperatures (Figure 2.22.b). To investigate whether the observed phenomena are inherent to CrPS₄ or influenced by contact resistance and answer the open questions presented in Section 2.5, we conducted 4-probe characterization on our multi-terminal CrPS₄ FETs.

But before that, it was necessary to select the most suitable device among the three different types of CrPS₄ FETs mentioned in Chapter 3: those with multilayer graphene contacts, gold contacts, and platinum contacts. Figure 4.1 shows the transfer curves of each device at $V_{ds} = 2$ V and at room temperature. Notably, the etched-graphene-contact device exhibits no tunability (Figure 4.1.a), indicating very poor contact quality. This may be attributed to the contamination of graphene by organic residuals during the nano-fabrication process. Actually, clear organic residuals on the graphene contacts were observed with AFM. Despite our attempts to remove them through deep UV cleaning and annealing, the residuals could not be effectively eliminated. As for the gold-contact device, it has both a top gate and a bottom gate, and both are working properly. However, the maximum current reached in our measurement is only 10 nA (Figure 4.1.b), indicating a large contact resistance. As mentioned in Chapter 3, the large contact resistance may be a result of the reduced contact area between CrPS₄ and the gold islands. As we cooled the system, the I_{ds} gradually decreases until lower than the noise level. So, we finally chose the platinum-contact device to do 4-probe characterization (Figure 4.1.c). It is worth mentioning that V_{th} is different between our devices, indicating different unintentional doping during the device fabrication process. All measurements presented in the following sections are ob-

Figure 4.1: The transfer curves of three representative pre-patterned CrPS₄ FET devices with (a) etched multilayer graphene, (b) gold, and (c) platinum as contact materials.

tained from the platinum-contact device depicted in Figure 4.1.c, unless otherwise stated.

After confirming the platinum as the contact material, the functionality of the top gate and bottom gate was evaluated. The transfer curves for both gates are presented in Figure 4.2. Notably, the V_{th} values obtained from the top-gate transfer curves are around 0. This implies that the Fermi surface is very close to the conduction band edge, indicating substantial n-type doping in our CrPS₄ flakes. Firstly, we compare the top-gate data with bottom-gate data obtained from the 2-probe method (Figure 4.2.a and c). Notably, it was observed that the top gate demonstrated superior performance compared to the bottom gate. Significant hysteresis was observed in the bottom gate transfer curves during forward and reverse sweeps from -60 V to 80 V . In contrast, the hysteresis was nearly absent in the top gate transfer curves. Both gates are tuning the same CrPS₄ flake at different interfaces, indicating that this hysteresis is not an intrinsic property of CrPS₄ but is due to extrinsic factors at different interfaces. The reason for the hysteresis observed in 2D material-based FETs was usually attribute to the formation of trap/defect states at the semiconductor/substrate interface [105], or the absorption of moisture at the semiconductor/gas interface [106]. During our device fabrication process, the top interface remains extremely clean due to direct contact with a fresh hBN layer. However, the bottom interface comes into contact with the bottom hBN and the pre-patterned bottom contacts, which were not clean after the lithography process. This suggests that organic residuals on the bottom hBN and the contacts may be responsible for the formation of trap states at the bottom interface. The difference between the threshold voltage in the forward scan and the reverse scan measures the number of trap states: $N_{Trap} = C[V_{th, Forward} - V_{th, Reverse}]/q$ [106][107]. For the back gate, the ΔV_{th} is very large ($\approx 40\text{ V}$), indicating a large number

Figure 4.2: (a) 2-probe transfer curves measured from the platinum-contact device at room temperature for the top gate ranging from -6 to 6 V. (b) 4-probe top-gate transfer curves measured simultaneously with (a). (c) 2-probe transfer curves measured at room temperature for the bottom gate ranging from -60 to 80 V. (d) 4-probe bottom-gate transfer curves measured simultaneously with (c).

of trap states.

Secondly, we compared the 2-probe and 4-probe transfer curves to know the magnitude and impact of the contact resistance at room temperature, which is shown in Figure 4.2.a and b. For the 2-probe method, the conductivity (after taking into account geometric factors) does not collapse for different biases. And the transfer curves show the sign of saturation at high gate voltages. These are the signs of the existence of contact resistance. For the 4-probe method, the conductivity is about 3 times that measured from the 2-probe method, indicating the contact resistance is very large. Platinum contacts are likely to form a large Schottky barrier with CrPS₄. As we know, 4-probe measurements are widely utilized because they can effectively mitigate the influence of contact resistance and provide more accurate measurements of the intrinsic properties of materials. In our

case, the 4-probe transfer curves show much better collapse (except for $V_{ds} = 0.5$ V) than that from 2-probe transfer curves. It seems that 4-probe measurements are effective in partially excluding the influence of contact resistance.

Figure 4.3: (a) 2-probe output characteristics of the Pt-contact device measured at room temperature at fixed V_{TG} ranging from 1 to 5 V. (d) 4-probe probe output characteristics measured simultaneously as (a). (c) 2-probe output characteristics of the Pt-contact device measured at room temperature at fixed V_{BG} ranging from 10 to 50 V. (d) 4-probe probe output characteristics measured simultaneously as (c).

The output curves provide further support for the aforementioned statements. Figures 4.3.a and b present the 2-probe and 4-probe output curves with a fixed top gate voltage ranging from 1 to 5 V. These plots clearly show that the 4-probe output curves exhibit much less non-linearity. While contact resistance is not entirely eliminated, its impact has been notably reduced through the implementation of 4-probe measurements. Similar outcomes were obtained with the bottom gate (V_{BG} ranging from 10 to 50 V), as depicted in Figures 4.3.c and d. This similarity indicates that top-gate and bottom-gate perform nearly equally well in mitigating the influence of contact resistance. These I - V curves

also exhibit asymmetry, with larger conductivity for positive bias than for negative bias, indicating the contact quality for the source and drain electrodes are different. Maybe it is due to their different interface quality after nano-fabrication.

All in all, our Pt-contact device also exhibited large contact resistance, which may originate from the formation of a large Schottky barrier between platinum and CrPS₄. However, with the application of 4-probe measurements, the impact of contact resistance appears to be reduced, although it hasn't been entirely removed. The reason why 4-probe measurements can not fully exclude the contact resistance might be attributed to the incorporation of vertical transport signal within our in-plane measurements, as will be discussed further in Section 4.4. In this study, the top gate was favored due to the better interface quality of the top hBN than the bottom hBN, which exhibits fewer trap states. Since we hope to exclude the influence of trap states and get accurate control over the charge carrier density. So, we perform the subsequent low-temperature measurements using the top gate only.

4.2 Functionality of Pt-contact CrPS₄ FETs persist at 2 K

Figure 4.4: (a) The 2-probe (blue line) and 4-probe (orange line) conductivity, which was already corrected for geometric factors, as a function of temperature. The measurements were conducted at fixed $V_{TG} = 7 \text{ V}$ and $V_{ds} = 2 \text{ V}$ during the cooling process from room temperature down to the base temperature of 2 K . (b) The first derivative of conductivity to temperature. Both curves show the same minimum at 26.8 K , which is the Néel temperature.

Following the characterization at room temperature, the Pt-contact device was subsequently cooled down from room temperature to 2 K in order to assess its performance at cryogenic temperatures and determine if there were any differences between the 4-probe and 2-probe measurements. Figure 4.4.a depicts the conductivity as a function of temperature during the cooling. The top gate voltage was kept at 7 V and $V_{ds} = 2$ V. As the temperature is cooled from room temperature to around 50 K, the conductivity monotonously decreases, which is due to the downshift of the Fermi level in the doped semiconductor. After that, the conductivity exhibits an increasing trend around the Néel temperature, consistent with the observations in Wu et al.'s graphene-contact devices [38], which was attributed to the onset of AFM order that suppresses disorder originating from spin fluctuations. Figure 4.4.b shows the dG/dT curves obtained from Figure 4.4.a, where the 4-probe method and 2-probe method seem to show the same minimum and yield the same $T_N = 26.8$ K. It is worth mentioning that the measured $T_N = 26.8$ K is significantly smaller than the reported 38 K from NPD experiments [29] and the 35 K from transport measurements [35] for bulk CrPS₄, but larger than the 23 K from optical measurements for few-layer CrPS₄ [84]. In this thesis, the thickness of the CrPS₄ flake was measured to be 8 nm, which corresponds to approximately 13 layers because monolayer CrPS₄ corresponds to 0.63 nm based on TEM cross-sectional imaging [83]. The crossover between bulk material and 2D material is not always well-defined [22], but a thickness of 8 nm is generally considered to be more like bulk material. So, the measured $T_N = 26.8$ K may have underestimated the actual T_N .

The potential underestimation of T_N could originate from two factors. Firstly, as detailed in Section 4.1, our CrPS₄ FET displays large contact resistance at room temperature, which can increase exponentially at lower temperatures due to the formation of a Schottky barrier between platinum and CrPS₄. Although 4-probe measurement can reduce the influence of contact resistance, it still cannot be entirely eliminated (as shown in Section 4.1). This contact resistance may have impacted the accurate determination of T_N . Secondly, because the noise in the derivative curve (Figure 4.4.b) can hinder the precise identification of the minimum point, the error of this method might be around 2-3 K. As a result, the determination of T_N by the minimum of dG/dT is not very reliable in our case.

Finally, we compare the 2-probe and 4-probe FET characterization at 2 K. Figure 4.5.a illustrates the 2-probe conductivity as a function of top gate voltage for different biases. The V_{th} at 2 K shows an increase of approximately 2 V compared to that at 295 K, consistent with previous reports [35]. This phenomenon has been attributed to the freeze-out of charge carriers in the dopants. Besides, these curves do not collapse onto each other, which is due to the non-linear 2-probe I - V curves as shown in Figure 4.5.c. Moreover, the pronounced non-linearity of the output curves at 2 K was previously reported in graphene-contact CrPS₄ FETs [35]. A similar phenomenon was also observed in graphene-contact NiI₂ FETs before, where linear I - V curves at 300 K transformed into highly nonlinear

curves at 15 K [37]. This is expected because the contact resistance shows a pronounced effect at low temperatures.

Figure 4.5: Characterization to the same CrPS₄ FET device as shown in Figure 4.1.c at 2 K. (a) 2-probe conductivity as a function of top gate voltage at different indicated biases. (b) 4-probe conductivity as a function of top gate voltage at the same biases as (a). (c) 2-probe output characteristics at V_{TG} ranging from 5 to 7 V. (d) 4-probe probe output characteristics at the same V_{TG} as (c).

It is observed that the 4-probe conductivity curves also do not collapse (Figure 4.5.b) because the 4-probe I - V curves become very non-linear at 2 K (Figure 4.5.d). As mentioned in the previous section, the observed extremely non-linear I - V characteristics may arise from the tunneling of electrons from the conducting channel on one side to the electrodes on the other side. In Section 4.4, we will demonstrate this phenomenon in detail.

4.3 Verification of intrinsic large magnetoconductance with multiterminal CrPS₄ FETs at 2 K

In the preceding sections, we successfully conducted fundamental characterizations of the CrPS₄ FET device at various temperatures, demonstrating its functionality at low temperatures. This enables us to do the magnetotransport study at 2 K. In this section, we will present the results of magneto-transport measurements on the Pt-contact device, aiming to answer the open questions presented in Section 2.5: 1. whether the previously reported large magnetoconductance [38] is from the graphene contact? 2. whether the contact resistance influences the determination of H_{flop} and H_{flip} ? 3. whether the gate-tuned magnetism is more pronounced in our thinner samples? Additionally, we will present the two parameters V_{th} and μ obtained from 4-terminal transfer curves, hoping to verify the mechanism underlying the observed large magnetoconductance at 2 K.

In order to study the first problem, we started by comparing the 2-probe and 4-probe magnetoconductance measurement results. Figure 4.6.a and b present the low-temperature conductivity as a function of the magnetic field. The measurements were conducted at 2 K. The 4-probe conductivity was found to be approximately 3 times larger than that obtained with the 2-probe method because the former method can mitigate the influence of contact resistance and remove the probe resistance. However, the 4-probe data is noisier than the 2-probe data, which is due to the additional error from the measurement of V_{xx} . Despite these differences, both methods consistently exhibit a large magnetoconductance (over 1000 %). Even though the absolute conductivity is very different, the magnetoconductance ($G(\mu H)/G(0) \times 100\%$) is very similar between the two methods. This finding provides strong evidence that the large magnetoconductance observed by Wu et al. [35] is not from graphene probes but rather an intrinsic property of CrPS₄.

In order to address the second question. We extract magnetic phase transition fields from the magneto-transport measurements. The spin-flop fields obtained from both methods were determined to be 0.6 T, which closely matches Wu et al.'s transport measurement results of multilayer CrPS₄ [35], and is only slightly smaller than the values obtained from NPD for bulk CrPS₄ (0.7 T [29]). On the other hand, the spin-flip magnetic phase transition fields were measured to be 7.8 T, which also aligns well with the previous study [35] and also matches the reported value of 8 T from NPD results [29]. Notably, the magnetic phase transition fields obtained from both 4-probe and 2-probe measurements agree with each other, proving that the determination of H_{flop} and H_{flip} from magneto-transport measurements is very accurate, regardless of contact resistance. Using transport measurements to investigate magnetic properties proves to be accurate and effective. This verifies that the previously reported large magnetoconductance [35][38] is indeed a result of the coupling with the magnetic state, rather than being influenced by contact resistance.

Figure 4.6: Conductivity as a function of the magnetic field for 2-probe (a) and 4-probe methods (b) separately. The measurements were conducted at 2 K with a bias of 2 V, with the top gate voltage ranging from 3.2 to 4 V. (c) Magnetoconductance curves obtained from 2-probe measurements in the spin-flop magnetic phase transition range from -1.2 to 1.2 T. (d) Magnetoconductance curves obtained from 2-probe measurements in the spin-flip magnetic phase transition range from -9 to -7 T.

As mentioned in Section 2.5.5, Wu et al. reported gate-tuned magnetism in their graphene-contact CrPS₄ FETs [35], where the application of a gate voltage induced a shift in the spin-flop and spin-flip fields. In this work, we indeed managed to exfoliate a thinner

CrPS₄ flake (8 nm) than theirs (10 nm) to fabricate our platinum-contact device. However, we may still struggle to observe an obvious shift of H_{flop} and H_{flip} for two reasons: firstly, 8 nm (13 L) is still considered too thick because the gate can only tune the charge carrier density in the first one or two layers; secondly, in Wu et al.'s study, they observed a shift of 20 mT in $\mu_0 H_{flop}$ and a shift of 0.3 T in $\mu_0 H_{flip}$ when the bottom gate voltage was increased by 35 V [35]. These shifts are already very small. In this thesis, the change in the top gate voltage is only 0.8 V, which corresponds to a 16 V bottom gate voltage change. As a result, the shifts in our work should be even smaller, making it very difficult to observe. Figure 4.6.c and d show the zoom-in magnetoconductance in the range of $\mu_0 H_{flop}$ and $\mu_0 H_{flip}$ respectively, where no noticeable shifts are observed. The next study should focus on developing a reliable and efficient exfoliation technique to obtain few-layer CrPS₄ flakes. With such thin flakes, the gate-tuned magnetism is expected to be more pronounced and easier to observe.

Figure 4.7: (a) 2-probe transfer curves of the Pt-contact device at $V_{ds} = 2$ V, with the vertical magnetic field increasing from 0 to 9 T. (b) 4-probe transfer curves obtained simultaneously with (a). (c) Linear fitting to the linear range of the 4-probe transfer curves shown in (c). (d) Threshold voltages and electron mobilities extracted from the linear fitting of the transfer curves shown in (c). All measurements were performed at 2 K.

Finally, as mentioned in Section 2.5.4, Wu et al. analyzed the dependence of V_{th} and μ (obtained from transfer curves) on temperature and magnetic field, and they were able to find two completely different mechanisms responsible for the large magnetoconductance observed by them [38]. However, in that section, we also mentioned that directly comparing transfer curves under different conditions overlooks possible changes in contact resistance and probe resistance. In this thesis, we hope to address this problem by performing the same experiments with 4-probe methods. Figure 4.7.(a) and (b) display the 2-probe and 4-probe transfer curves measured at 2 K, respectively. Both 2-probe and 4-probe data consistently show the same trend: as the magnetic field is increased from 0 to 9 T, the V_{th} shifts to lower values while the μ (slope of the linear region) shifts to higher values. The downshift of V_{th} confirms the phenomenon observed from Wu et al.'s graphene-contact devices, which is indeed due to the magnetic phase transition of CrPS₄ that causes the downshift in its conduction band edge. However, contrary to their report of unchanged μ , we also observed an increase in charge carrier mobility, as summarized in Figure 4.7.d (orange square). This increase is likely due to the inclusion of the vertical transport signal, which cannot be effectively excluded with our 4-probe methods because of the special contact geometry (top gate and bottom contacts), as explained in the following section.

4.4 Evidence of c-axis tunnel signal observed in in-plane transport measurements

We found multiple pieces of evidence suggesting the inclusion of vertical transport signals in both 2-probe and 4-probe measurements. Firstly, unexpected kinks are observed at around 3 T and 5 T (see Figure 4.6.a and b), which were not reported before. The positions of these kinks also exhibit a shift with varying top gate voltage. One notable difference between our top-gate platinum-contact FETs and previously reported bottom-gate graphene-contact devices [35][38] is the contact geometry, where our contacts and the conducting channel are not on the same side of the CrPS₄. It is well known that standard 4-probe measurements can effectively remove contact resistance. However, in this peculiar bottom-contact geometry, the 4-probe signal can inadvertently include in the vertical transport signal due to electron tunneling from the conducting channel on one side to the electrodes on the other side of the CrPS₄ flake. Actually, our group has collected unpublished data on the vertical transport properties of CrPS₄ with the same thicknesses (13 L), which indeed show the peaks of tunneling resistance at 3 T and 5 T. The peaks in the tunneling resistance increase the overall resistance, consequently decreasing the measured conductivity. This explains the observed kinks in the magnetoconductance curves at around 3 T and 5 T (Figure 4.6.a and b).

Furthermore, the inclusion of the vertical transport signal can also explain the observed

enhancement of charge carrier mobility at higher magnetic fields (see Figure 4.7.c and d). Our unpublished data show that at higher magnetic fields, the tunnel resistance becomes significantly smaller compared to that at 0 field. For a 13-layer CrPS₄ tunnel junction sample, the tunnel resistance at 9 T decreases by 80% compared to the tunnel resistance at 0 field. This reduction in resistance facilitates the transport of electrons, resulting in an increase in charge carrier mobility.

Figure 4.8: (a) 2-probe magnetoconductance as a function of the vertical magnetic field at different temperatures ranging from 10 to 60 K. The measurements were performed at $V_{ds} = 2 \text{ V}$ and $V_{TG} = 7 \text{ V}$. (b) 2-probe magnetoconductance at 10 T ($G_{\mu_0 H=10 \text{ T}} / G_{\mu_0 H=0} \times 100\%$) for different temperatures. (c) 4-probe magnetoconductance obtained at the same condition with (a). (d) 4-probe magnetoconductance at 10 T for different temperatures.

To further validate that the observed unusual kinks in the magnetoconductance curves

arise from the vertical transport signal, we conducted additional measurements of magnetoconductance at different temperatures ranging from 10 to 90 K. As shown in Figure 4.8.(a) and (c), both the 2-probe and 4-probe magnetoconductance exhibit the kinks at low temperatures, and it is evident that the kinks persist until 35 K. However, as the temperature is raised above 40 K, these kinks disappear. This behavior is consistent with our unpublished data, which indicates that the oscillations in the vertical transport signal disappear above 35 K, which is the Néel temperature of multilayer CrPS₄ [35]. Therefore, this provides additional evidence that the observed kinks originate from the unintentionally included tunneling signal that could not be excluded with 4-probe measurements. Intriguingly, we observed that the magnetoconductance at 10 T ($G_{\mu_0 H=10\text{ T}}/G_{\mu_0 H=0} \times 100\%$) exhibits a peak at 50 K (see Figure 4.8.b and d), which is significantly larger than the Néel temperature of the multilayer CrPS₄ used in this thesis. This behavior deviates from previous reports [108] on field-effect transistors based on multilayer VI₃. The mechanism responsible for this phenomenon still requires further exploration and investigation.

4.5 Conclusion

In summary, we unprecedentedly fabricated multiterminal CrPS₄ FETs with platinum as contact material. We firstly did 2-probe and 4-probe characterization to the CrPS₄ FET at room temperature, finding the top gate has much better quality, which shows zero hysteresis in the transfer curves. This is because the top hBN has a fresh exfoliated interface whereas the bottom hBN goes through a nano-fabrication process that left it with trap states. We also found a large contact resistance due to the formation of the Schottky barrier between platinum and CrPS₄. Fortunately, with the 4-probe measurements, we can partially remove the influence of contact resistance and get much less non-linear $I - V$ curves. We also did FET characterization at 2 K and demonstrated the functionality of our device at low temperatures, which allows us to perform magneto-transport measurements on it.

In order to verify the phenomenon reported by Wu et al. [35][38], we measured magnetoconductance with 2-probe and 4-probe methods. Firstly, we confirmed the phenomenon of large magnetoconductance (over 1000%) is indeed an intrinsic property of CrPS₄, rather than the property of graphene contacts. Secondly, we confirmed the accuracy and effectiveness of determining H_{flop} and H_{flop} from the magneto-transport measurements. The values of H_{flop} and H_{flop} agree well with Wu et al.'s results [35] and also the results from NPD measurement [29]. However, even with a thinner CrPS₄ flake, we still didn't observe a discernible shift of H_{flop} and H_{flop} with gate, because the tuning range of V_{TG} is too small. The gate-tuned magnetism is expected to be more pronounced and easier to observe at few-layer CrPS₄ flakes. Besides, we analyzed the dependence of V_{th} and μ (obtained from transfer curves) on the magnetic field. In addition to confirming the

down-shift of V_{th} , we also found the obvious increase in μ at higher fields, which may originate from the incorporation of tunnel signal in our in-plane measurements.

We provided multiple pieces of evidence showing that the c-axis tunnel signal is indeed observed in our measurements. Firstly, obvious kinks are observed in the magnetoconductance measurements at around 3 T and 5 T, which agree well with the peaks of tunneling resistance. What's more, these kinks disappear above 35 K, which is the Néel temperature of multilayer CrPS₄ [35]. This is due to our unique contact geometry (top gate and bottom contacts), where electrons tunnel back and forth from the conducting channel on one side to the electrodes on the opposite side of CrPS₄. This effect may be minimized if CrPS₄ is thinned to 1 or 2 layers, where the conducting channel occupies the entire flake so that no vertical transport happens.

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